

Flora Assessment of Selected Farms on the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment

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- **mapped habitat data in GIS-compatible format, including shapefiles and KMZ files where applicable;**
- **plant species list for the study area and associated biodiversity observation records, where applicable, obtainable from <https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/kwamandlangampisi-pe-biodiversity-stewardship-site>;**
- **list of conservation-important species recorded during the assessment, and any additional supporting files generated during the assessment process;**
- **supporting photographic records from the field survey, spatial data and associated map outputs used in the assessment are obtainable from the Intando Yemvelo repository in the same Zenodo Community.**

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Executive Summary

The Biodiversity Company was appointed to undertake a botanical assessment of eight separately managed farms within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment. The purpose of the study was to characterise the vegetation and habitat types present, assess habitat condition, compile a flora species list, identify species of conservation importance, record invasive alien plants, and provide management recommendations to support the long-term ecological sustainability of the area.

The assessment was undertaken using a combination of desktop review and field survey. Prior to fieldwork, an expected species list and overview of vegetation types and Species of Conservation Concern were compiled using available records from the National Screening Tool, GBIF, iNaturalist, and the BRAHMS online plant database. Field surveys were conducted during two survey periods, from 24 November to 3 December 2025 and from 15 to 20 February 2026, in order to improve seasonal coverage and increase the likelihood of detecting a wider range of flora. All major habitat types present within the study area were surveyed, including grasslands, wetlands, riparian areas, rocky habitats, and forest patches.

A total of 1 358 botanical observations were recorded, representing 797 unique species from 157 plant families. The flora was dominated by species-rich grassland and forb-associated families, with Asteraceae, Orchidaceae, Fabaceae, Poaceae, Asparagaceae, and Iridaceae being the most species-rich. At habitat level, Dolerite Grasslands supported the greatest number of observations and the highest species richness, followed by Northern Afromontane Forest, Sandstone Grasslands, and Wetland/Riparian Vegetation. These habitats were also the most important from a conservation perspective and supported the majority of the species of botanical significance recorded during the assessment.

The study area falls within a landscape of high biodiversity importance. The PAOI overlaps principally with a Least Concern ecosystem and marginally with an Endangered ecosystem and is situated within the broader Wakkerstroom Key Biodiversity Area. It also falls within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment and overlaps biodiversity priority areas identified in the Mpumalanga Biodiversity Sector Plan. This broader landscape context is consistent with the floristic richness and ecological sensitivity observed during the survey.

A total of 14 Species of Conservation Concern were recorded during the assessment, including Endangered, Vulnerable, Near Threatened, and Rare taxa. These included species such as *Alepidea cordifolia*, *Brachystelma gerrardii*, *Dierama erectum*, *Gerbera aurantiaca*, *Dracosciadium italaie*, *Dioscorea sylvatica*, *Prunus africana*, and *Disa maculomarronina*. In addition, seven rare species, ten range-extended species, five potential new or taxonomically uncertain taxa, two decreasing species, and three nationally protected tree species were recorded. These findings confirm the high botanical significance of the study area and highlight the importance of maintaining intact grassland, wetland, riparian, rocky, and forest habitats.

The farms differed considerably in terms of ecological condition and management pressure. Groothoek 171/4 was identified as one of the most intact and botanically significant farms, with very good veld condition, low grazing pressure, negligible alien invasion, and highly distinctive summit wetlands and sheet rock habitats. Groothoek 171/3 and Donkerhoek 172/2 were also assessed as being in relatively good condition, although each requires continued monitoring and careful management of grazing, fire, and localised invasions. Other farms, including Groothoek 171/2, Groothoek 171/R, Groothoek 171/1, Donkerhoek 172/4, and Roodewal 190/1, showed more evident signs of ecological pressure, particularly from alien plant invasion, grazing pressure, wetland disturbance, plantation edge effects, bracken fern dominance, or habitat transformation.

Alien invasive plant management emerged as a major management priority across much of the study area. The most important alien invasive species recorded or noted include *Acacia mearnsii*, *Acacia dealbata*, *Eucalyptus* spp., *Pinus pinaster*, *Populus* spp., *Solanum mauritianum*, and *Lantana camara*,

together with the problematic indigenous invader *Pteridium aquilinum* (Bracken fern). These species are having a substantial effect on habitat quality in certain farms, particularly in riparian areas, forest margins, old lands, and disturbed grasslands. Their control will require a long-term, structured programme with repeated follow-up.

From a management perspective, the long-term sustainability of the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment will depend on adaptive veld management informed by regular monitoring. Grazing systems should include sufficient rest and avoid continuous pressure on the same areas, while fire management should follow a patch mosaic approach that supports biodiversity and avoids repeated blanket burning. Sensitive habitats such as wetlands, riparian zones, summit areas, rocky outcrops, and forest margins should receive additional protection and monitoring. Alien invasive plants should be managed proactively, and forest edges should be monitored carefully as priority zones for invasion and ecological change.

Overall, the assessment confirms that the surveyed farms support a species-rich and conservation-important flora within a highly significant montane grassland landscape. Despite varying levels of ecological pressure between farms, the area as a whole retains substantial biodiversity value and remains important for the conservation of grassland, wetland, riparian, and forest-associated flora within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment. With appropriate management, the ecological integrity of these farms can be maintained and, in some cases, improved over time.

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1 Introduction

The Biodiversity Company was appointed to undertake a Botanical Assessment for the proposed project within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment. The purpose of the assessment was to identify and describe the botanical characteristics of the study area, including the vegetation types present, the ecological condition of habitats, the floristic composition, the occurrence of threatened and range-extended plant species, and the presence and extent of invasive alien plant species. The assessment further aimed to provide recommendations for the sustainable management of natural habitats within the study area.

1.1 Site Location

The KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment is located in southern Mpumalanga Province, South Africa, within the Pixley ka Seme Local Municipality and the Mkhondo Local Municipality, along the northern border of KwaZulu-Natal (Figure 1-1). The protected environment is situated in the broader Wakkerstroom–Lüneburg area and lies within a region of high biodiversity importance. The protected environment covers an area of approximately 27,641 ha and comprises numerous farm portions managed under a broader protected area framework (MTPA, 2025).

Only a selected number of farms (8) were surveyed. These selected farms made up the Project Area of Influence (PAOI) and was comprised of the following farms: Groothoek 171/R, Groothoek 171/1, Groothoek 171/2, Groothoek 171/3, Groothoek 171/4, Donkerhoek 172/2, Donkerhoek 172/4, and Roodewal 190/1 (Figure 1-2).

Figure 1-1 Map illustrating the regional context of the Project Area of Influence (PAOI).

Figure 1-2 Map illustrating the overall PAOI.

1.2 Project Description

The study is intended to provide a botanical baseline for each of the eight farms, to support landowners and biodiversity managers in understanding the botanical and ecological characteristics, condition, and management priorities of the area. Given that the farms are managed separately, each property is treated as an individual management unit for the purposes of this assessment.

1.3 Scope of Work

The scope of work for this botanical assessment included the completion of a baseline study across eight separately managed farms within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment. The assessment focused on the identification, description, and mapping of vegetation and habitat features, together with the evaluation of their ecological condition and management requirements.

More specifically, the scope of work included the following:

- Delineate and map all vegetation types;
- Determine the ecological state of all habitat types within the project area. Provide recommendations for management measures to ensure long term sustainability.
- Compile a flora species list.
- Create an Inaturalist project for the surveyed area;
- Identify type, extent and distribution of invasive alien species. Provide recommendations on IAP removal.

- Provide recommendations for the sustainable management of all habitats within the project area.

1.4 Deliverables

The following deliverables form part of this botanical assessment and associated project outputs for the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment study area:

- Botanical Assessment Report;
- mapped habitat data in GIS-compatible format, including shapefiles and KMZ files where applicable;
- plant species list for the study area;
- list of conservation-important species recorded during the assessment;
- supporting photographic records from the field survey;
- spatial data and associated map outputs used in the assessment;
- iNaturalist project and associated biodiversity observation records, where applicable; and
- any additional supporting files generated during the assessment process.

2 Approach

This botanical assessment was undertaken through a desktop review, field survey, and spatial interpretation. A desktop assessment of the vegetation types occurring within the study area, as well as the potential Species of Conservation Concern (SCCs) likely to occur on site, was completed prior to fieldwork. This was undertaken to inform the survey design and to maximise the likelihood of detecting rare, threatened, or otherwise significant plant species during the field assessment. The desktop component made use of available biodiversity screening information together with occurrence records from GBIF, the national screening tool and iNaturalist.

Two field visits were undertaken as part of the assessment. The initial survey was conducted from 24 November to 3 December 2025, followed by a second survey from 15 to 20 February 2026. Conducting surveys during different parts of the growing season improved floristic coverage and increased the likelihood of detecting species with different flowering and growth periods.

All habitat types occurring within the study area were surveyed, including wetlands and riparian areas, forest habitats, and grassland habitats. During the field assessment, vegetation and habitat types were observed and described, plant species were recorded, and areas of ecological sensitivity, disturbance, and invasive alien plant occurrence were noted. Particular attention was given to threatened flora, range-extended species, and other species of conservation importance.

Field observations were used to support the delineation and mapping of vegetation and habitat types, the compilation of flora species lists, the identification of invasive alien plant species, and the assessment of habitat condition. These findings were then interpreted in the context of the broader ecological setting of the PAOI within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment in order to develop management recommendations aimed at supporting the long-term sustainability of the assessed farms.

Figure 2-1 *Field survey sample points.*

2.1 Assumptions and Limitations

The following assumptions and limitations are applicable for this assessment:

- Only two site visits were conducted with which we were able to observe and identify a large number of species; however, winter flowering species may have been missed due to seasonality. This assessment however is considered sufficient to derive a meaningful baseline;
- While every effort is made to cover as much of the site as possible, representative sampling is completed, and by its nature, it is likely that some plant species that are present on site were not recorded during the field investigations; and
- The Global Positioning System (GPS) used in the assessment has an accuracy of 5 m, and consequently, any spatial features may be offset by 5 m.

3 Desktop Analysis

3.1 Ecologically Important Landscape Features

A review of the relevant biodiversity planning and conservation datasets was done to place the Project Area of Influence (PAOI) within its broader ecological and conservation context. These datasets provide an indication of the biodiversity importance of the area at both ecosystem and landscape level and help to identify whether the PAOI overlaps with threatened ecosystems, biodiversity priority areas, or recognised sites of national or international conservation importance. In this assessment, the Red List of Ecosystems, the Mpumalanga Biodiversity Sector Plan, and the Key Biodiversity Areas dataset were considered.

Together, these datasets show that the PAOI falls within a landscape of high biodiversity importance associated with the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment and the broader Wakkerstroom region. The section below therefore provides a summary of the ecosystem threat status associated with the PAOI, its relationship to provincial biodiversity priority areas, and its overlap with the Wakkerstroom Key Biodiversity Area. This information provides important context for interpreting the botanical findings of the study and for understanding the conservation significance of the habitats and species recorded within the PAOI.

3.1.1.1 Red List of Ecosystems

The Ecosystem Threat Status is an indicator of an ecosystem's wellbeing, based on the level of change in structure, function or composition. Ecosystem types are categorised as Critically Endangered (CR), Endangered (EN), Vulnerable (VU) or Least Concern (LC), based on the proportion of the original extent of each ecosystem type that remains in good ecological condition. According to the Red List of Ecosystems dataset (Skowno & Monyeki, 2021) the PAOI overlaps marginally with an EN ecosystem and principally with a LC ecosystem (Figure 3-1).

Figure 3-1 Map illustrating the ecosystem threat status associated with the PAOI

3.1.1.2 Provincial Conservation Plan

The key output of this systematic biodiversity plan is a map of biodiversity priority areas (MBSP, 2023). The MBSP CBA map delineates Critical Biodiversity Areas, Ecological Support Areas, Other Natural Areas, Protected Areas, and areas that have been irreversibly modified from their natural state (MTPA, 2014). The MBSP uses the following terms to categorise the various land used types according to their biodiversity and environmental importance:

- Critical Biodiversity Area (CBA);
- Ecological Support Area (ESA);
- Other Natural Area (ONA);
- Protected Area (PA); and
- Moderately or Heavily Modified Areas (MMA's or HMA's).

According to the MBSP Terrestrial dataset, the PAOI overlaps with a Protected Environment, which is expected. It is interesting to note that Roodewal is not within the Protected Environment according to this dataset (Figure 3-2).

Figure 3-2 Map illustrating the PAOI in relation to the Mpumalanga Terrestrial Biodiversity Spatial Plan

3.1.1.3 Key Biodiversity Areas

A new set of Key Biodiversity Areas (KBA) specific to South Africa has been identified using the Global Standard for the Identification of Key Biodiversity Areas version 1.2 (IUCN 2016), applied to South African species and ecosystems. KBAs are critical sites that play a vital role in maintaining global biodiversity by serving as essential habitats for species. The identification of KBAs enables governments and civil society to pinpoint key locations crucial for species and their habitats worldwide. This understanding facilitates collaborative efforts to manage and conserve these areas, thereby safeguarding global biological diversity and supporting international biodiversity objectives.

Unlike the Important Bird Areas (IBAs), which primarily focus on birds, the KBA framework encompasses a broader spectrum of biodiversity, including mammals, amphibians, plants, and other taxa. BirdLife South Africa (BLSA), in consultation with the KBA National Coordination Group, has opted to retire IBAs and integrate KBAs into its conservation strategy. This strategic shift acknowledges the necessity of investing resources effectively to protect avian and other macroecological elements at the site level within a comprehensive framework of biodiversity conservation (KBA NCG, 2024).

According to the KBA dataset, the PAOI overlaps with the Wakkerstroom KBA (Figure 3-3). According to the KBA metadata, this site qualifies as a Key Biodiversity Area of international significance and meets the thresholds for three criteria described in the Global Standard for the Identification of Key Biodiversity Areas. Based on current available information, 29 species meet one or more KBA criteria for this site. The KBA trigger species at this site include birds, butterflies, fish, and plants. The site meets criterion A1 due to the presence of significant proportions of the global populations of 16 threatened species. The site regularly holds 16 geographically restricted species, thereby meeting criterion B1. Assemblages of co-occurring range-restricted species in the Aves and Gentianales taxonomic groups regularly present within the site meet criterion B2. A quantitative analysis of irreplaceability indicates

that the site is 100% irreplaceable for the global persistence of seven species, thereby meeting criterion E. In addition, the site holds significant proportions of the global extent of two threatened ecosystems, thereby meeting criterion A2, and one geographically restricted ecosystem, thereby meeting criterion B4.

The Wakkerstroom KBA is a large terrestrial site with limited formal protection, located in KwaZulu-Natal and Mpumalanga. A substantial portion of the site forms part of the escarpment landscape linking the southern and northern Drakensberg. The site straddles this divide and comprises low mountains and undulating plains. Vegetation is dominated by short montane grasslands on plateaus and relatively flat areas, with short forest and *Leucosidea* thickets occurring along steep, mainly east-facing slopes and drainage areas. *Leucosidea sericea* is identified as the dominant woody pioneer species invading areas affected by grazing mismanagement. The site further includes undulating plains with moderately steep slopes, while valley basins are generally wide and flat, and mountainous terrain is concentrated mostly along the northern and eastern boundaries. The grasslands are described as tall closed grassland rich in forbs and dominated by *Tristachya leucothrix*, *Themeda triandra*, and *Hyparrhenia hirta*, while evergreen woody vegetation is associated with rocky outcrops.

The delineation of the KBA is based on refinement of the existing Important Bird and Biodiversity Area and includes the large protected environment, intact grassland vegetation, and numerous important wetlands. Parts of the site are also identified as Critical Biodiversity Areas and Strategic Water Source Areas. The site is managed primarily by a regional conservation authority responsible for regulating land use change in Critical Biodiversity Areas and threatened ecosystems, with part of the site additionally managed by a catchment management authority.

The ecosystems listed as contributing to the biodiversity significance of the KBA include Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland, classified as Least Concern (LC), Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland, classified as Endangered (EN), and Northern Zululand Mistbelt Grassland, also classified as Endangered (EN).

The biodiversity elements triggering the KBA criteria include a number of bird species of high conservation importance. These include *Hemimacronyx chloris* (Yellow-breasted Pipit), listed as Vulnerable (VU); *Sarothrura ayresii* (White-winged Flufftail), listed as Critically Endangered (CR); *Spizocorys fringillaris* (Botha's Lark), listed as Endangered (EN); *Sylvia nigricapillus* (Bush Blackcap), listed as Vulnerable (VU); *Geronticus calvus* (Southern Bald Ibis), listed as Vulnerable (VU); *Balearica regulorum* (Grey Crowned Crane), listed as Endangered (EN); *Bucconyx carunculatus* (Wattled Crane), listed as Vulnerable (VU); *Heteromirafra ruddi* (Rudd's Lark), listed as Endangered (EN); and *Anthropoides paradiseus* (Blue Crane), listed as Vulnerable (VU).

Among the plant taxa, *Dierama erectum* is listed as Endangered (EN), *Dracosciadium italaie* as Vulnerable (VU), *Aspidoglossum xanthosphaerum* as Vulnerable (VU), *Aspidoglossum demissum* as Vulnerable (VU), and *Polygala praticola* as Vulnerable (VU). Additional plant trigger species listed for the site include *Holothrix majubensis*, *Khadia alticola*, *Xysmalobium pedifoetidum*, *Bowkeria citrina*, *Lotononis amajubica*, and Aloeides-related taxa where relevant to the broader site assemblage.

The invertebrate trigger species include *Aloeides titei* (Tite's Copper), *Aloeides merces* (Wakkerstroom Copper), *Dingana alaedeus* (Wakkerstroom Widow), *Orachrysops lacrimosa* (Restless Blue), and *Stygionympha curlei* (Curle's Hillside Brown). In the freshwater fish group, *Chiloglanis emarginatus* (Phongolo Suckermouth) is listed as Vulnerable (VU).

Figure 3-3 Map illustrating the PAOI in relation to the Key Biodiversity Areas dataset

3.2 Flora Assessment

This section is divided into a description of the vegetation type expected under natural conditions and the expected flora species.

3.2.1 Vegetation Types

From a botanical perspective, the study area is associated with Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland, Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland, and Northern Afrotemperate Forest (Mucina & Rutherford, 2006). Together, these vegetation types form part of the broader montane and moist highland landscape of southern Mpumalanga and northern KwaZulu-Natal and are well recognised for their floristic richness and biogeographical importance. This broader vegetation context is reflected in the high diversity of herbs, graminoids, geophytes, shrubs, and woody species recorded during the assessment. The vegetation units are shown in (Figure 3-4).

3.2.1.1 Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland

Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland is a high-altitude vegetation type occurring from approximately 1 440 to 2 200 m above sea level. Botanically, it is characterised by short montane grassland occupying plateaus and undulating uplands, with associated short forest patches and Leucosidea thickets occurring along steeper slopes and drainage lines. The vegetation is typically dominated by a diverse and ecologically important grass layer, with species such as *Themeda triandra*, *Tristachya leucothrix*, *Hyparrhenia hirta*, *Harpochoa falx*, *Trachypogon spicatus*, *Heteropogon contortus*, *Cymbopogon caesius*, *Digitaria tricholaenoides*, *Eragrostis chloromelas*, and *Microchloa caffra* all characteristic of the unit. These grasses create the structural matrix within which a rich herbaceous flora occurs.

The forb and geophyte component of Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland is particularly important from a botanical perspective. Characteristic herbaceous taxa include species such as *Berkheya*

onopordifolia var. *glabra*, *Cephalaria natalensis*, *Pelargonium luridum*, *Aster bakerianus*, *Berkheya setifera*, *Helichrysum cephaloideum*, *H. cooperi*, *H. monticola*, *H. nudifolium* var. *nudifolium*, *H. oreophilum*, *Pentanisia prunelloides* subsp. *latifolia*, *Sebaea leiostyla*, *Selago densiflora*, and *Vernonia natalensis*. The geophytic component is also well developed and includes taxa such as *Agapanthus inapertus* subsp. *intermedius*, *Asclepias aurea*, *Corycium dracomontanum*, *Disa versicolor*, *Eucomis bicolor*, *Gladiolus ecklonii*, *Hesperantha coccinea*, *Hypoxis costata*, *Hypoxis rigidula* var. *pilosissima*, *Moraea brevistyla*, *Rhodohypoxis baurii* var. *confecta*, and *Cyrтанthus tuckii* var. *transvaalensis*. Together, these species reflect the high floristic diversity and seasonal expression that are typical of relatively intact montane grassland.

This vegetation type is also important because it supports several biogeographically important and endemic taxa. Species such as *Bowkeria citrina*, *Lotononis amajubica*, and *Aloe modesta* are noted as biogeographically important, while taxa such as *Helichrysum aureum* var. *argenteum*, *Selago longicalyx*, *Nerine platypetala*, and *Asparagus fractiflexus* contribute to its endemic component. The unit is further notable for representing the northern distribution limit of a number of Drakensberg-associated species, while also containing elements more typical of the northern escarpment flora. This transitional and biogeographically complex character helps explain the presence of several notable species in the study area, including taxa that are rare, range-extended, or of conservation concern.

3.2.2 Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland

Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland occurs at somewhat lower elevations, generally between 920 and 1 500 m above sea level, and is characterised botanically by tall, closed, forb-rich grassland. The grass layer is dominated by species such as *Tristachya leucothrix*, *Themeda triandra*, *Hyparrhenia hirta*, *Monocymbium cerasiiforme*, *Loudetia simplex*, *Setaria nigrirostris*, *Harpochoa falx*, *Andropogon schirensis*, *Brachiaria serrata*, *Ctenium concinnum*, *Cymbopogon caesius*, and *Eragrostis racemosa*. This tall, dense grassland structure supports a rich and varied herbaceous flora, particularly where burning and grazing regimes remain suitable for forb persistence.

The forb flora of Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland is diverse and includes species such as *Argyrolobium speciosum*, *Cissus diversilobata*, *Dicoma zeyheri*, *Eriosema kraussianum*, *Geranium wakkerstroomianum*, *Helichrysum nudifolium* var. *nudifolium*, *Ipomoea oblongata*, *Pelargonium luridum*, *Acalypha glandulifolia*, *Berkheya setifera*, *Dicoma anomala*, *Euryops laxus*, *E. transvaalensis* subsp. *setilobus*, *Indigofera hilaris* var. *hilaris*, *Kohautia amatymbica*, *Pearsonia grandifolia*, *Pentanisia prunelloides* subsp. *latifolia*, *Senecio bupleuroides*, *S. coronatus*, and *Vernonia capensis*. The geophytic flora is equally prominent and includes taxa such as *Chlorophytum haygarthii*, *Gladiolus aurantiacus*, *Agapanthus inapertus* subsp. *intermedius*, *Asclepias aurea*, *Cyrтанthus tuckii* var. *transvaalensis*, *Hypoxis colchicifolia*, *Hypoxis costata*, *Moraea brevistyla*, *Watsonia latifolia*, and *Zantedeschia rehmannii*. Succulent and shrubby elements, including *Aloe ecklonis*, *Aloe maculata*, *Lopholaena segmentata*, *Calpurnia sericea*, and *Rhus rehmanniana*, also contribute to the floristic character of this vegetation type.

From a botanical perspective, Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland is significant because it supports a rich and often visually prominent flora, especially in the forb-rich grassland layer and around rocky outcrops, drainage features, and deeper moist soils. The vegetation type also contains several low escarpment endemics and locally important taxa, including *Bowkeria citrina*, *Lotononis amajubica*, *Hemizygia macrophylla*, *Aloe modesta*, and *Aloe reitzii* var. *vernalis*. However, unlike Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland, this vegetation type is regarded as Vulnerable, with a substantial proportion already transformed by plantation forestry and cultivation. Heavy livestock grazing, altered fire regimes, and invasive alien plants also place pressure on the floristic composition, especially through the loss of forb diversity and the simplification of the grassland structure.

3.2.3 Northern Afrotropical Forest

The Northern Afrotropical Forest comprises low, relatively species-poor forests of afrotemperate origin that occur as small, high-altitude patches in mountain kloofs and on scarps and sheltered slopes. These forests are distributed across parts of the Free State, KwaZulu-Natal, Mpumalanga, North West, Gauteng, Limpopo, and Lesotho, generally between about 1 450 and 1 900 m above sea level, although outliers occur both lower and higher. Along the eastern escarpment, they occur from Van Reenen's Pass to the Pongola Bush area near Piet Retief. In structural terms, these forests are typically low in stature, reaching up to about 20 m in the Low Escarpment region, and are associated with cool, moist, sheltered habitat such as mountain ravines, sub-ridge scarps, and protected slopes

Floristically, the canopy is typically dominated by species such as *Podocarpus latifolius*, *Olinia emarginata*, *Halleria lucida*, and *Scolopia mundii*, with *Afrocarpus falcatus* also recorded as an important tall tree component. In somewhat drier expressions of the forest, species such as *Pittosporum viridiflorum*, *Celtis africana*, *Mimusops zeyheri*, *Nuxia congesta*, and *Combretum erythrophyllum* may become more prominent, while *Xymalos monospora* may dominate mistbelt expressions in northern KwaZulu-Natal. Other characteristic woody species include *Rothmannia capensis*, *Dais cotinifolia*, *Ilex mitis*, *Buddleja saligna*, *Bowkeria verticillata*, *Calpurnia aurea*, *Diospyros whyteana*, *Leucosidea sericea*, and *Canthium ciliatum*. The understorey includes a range of shrubs, herbs, ferns, and graminoids, including taxa such as *Plectranthus fruticosus*, *Hypoestes aristata*, *Streptocarpus haygarthii*, *Peperomia retusa*, *Oplismenus hirtellus*, and *Schoenoxiphium lehmannii*. Endemic or noteworthy taxa associated with this forest type include *Scolopia oreophila*, *Maytenus albata*, *Sparrmannia ricinocarpa*, and *Streptocarpus polyanthus subsp. dracomontanus*

From a conservation perspective, Northern Afrotropical Forest is regarded as least threatened at a broad scale, although it remains sensitive to local disturbance. Threats noted for this vegetation type include hot fires entering from surrounding vegetation, uncontrolled timber extraction, medicinal plant harvesting, and grazing within forest patches. In the context of the study area, this vegetation type is botanically important because even relatively small forest patches can support protected tree species, forest-margin specialists, and locally rare or declining taxa, thereby contributing significantly to habitat heterogeneity and overall floristic diversity.

Figure 3-4 Map illustrating the vegetation types associated with the PAOI

3.3 Expected Species of Conservation Concern

The species were obtained from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), National Screening Tool, iNaturalist and the Brahms online plant database.

A list of the expected species for the surrounding area was generated and is shown in Figure 3-5. The list was compiled using records obtained from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the National Screening Tool, iNaturalist, and the BRAHMS online plant database. The purpose of compiling this list was to identify species of conservation importance that are known from the broader area, or that may reasonably be expected to occur within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment based on available records and habitat suitability.

The expected species list includes taxa that were confirmed during the present study, taxa previously recorded within or near the study area, and species considered likely to occur based on the presence of suitable habitat. Likelihood of occurrence was assigned based on a combination of available locality records, habitat availability within the study area, and broader distribution patterns. Species with a high likelihood of occurrence were generally those that were confirmed during the assessment, previously recorded from the study area by other observers, or known from nearby localities with suitable habitat present onsite. Species assigned a medium or low likelihood of occurrence were typically those with fewer nearby records, more marginal distributions, or more specific habitat requirements that may only occur locally within the study area.

A number of the expected species were confirmed during the present assessment, including *Alepidea cordifolia*, *Aloe hlangapies*, *Brachystelma gerrardii*, *Curtisia dentata*, *Dierama erectum*, *Dioscorea sylvatica*, *Disa maculomarronina*, *Dracosciadium italaе*, *Gerbera aurantiaca*, and *Merwillia plumbea*. Additional species such as *Aloe kniphofioides*, *Aloe modesta*, *Aspidoglossum demissum*, *Protea parvula*, and *Brachystelma remotum* do occur within the study area based on existing observations by others.

Several further species of conservation importance were not recorded during the current survey, but remain likely or potentially likely to occur due to the presence of suitable habitat. These include *Gladiolus paludosus*, *Melanospermum italaе*, *Satyrium microrrhynchum*, *Habenaria culveri*, *Nerine gracilis*, *Nerine platypetala*, *Aspidoglossum xanthosphaerum*, *Xerophyta vallispongolana*, and *Searsia dracomontana*. The absence of these taxa from the present survey should not necessarily be interpreted as true absence, as detectability may be influenced by seasonality, flowering period, local abundance, survey timing, and the patchy distribution of suitable microhabitat.

A smaller number of expected species were assessed as having a lower likelihood of occurrence within the study area. In these cases, the reduced likelihood reflects limited nearby records, the position of the site near the edge of the species' known range, or the possibility that local climatic conditions may be suboptimal. Examples include *Clivia miniata* var. *miniata*, *Ocotea kenyensis*, *Ocotea bullata*, *Searsia harveyi*, and *Encephalartos natalensis*.

Overall, the expected species list provides useful context for the interpretation of the survey results and highlights the broader botanical potential of the study area. It demonstrates that the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment falls within a floristically important landscape capable of supporting additional species of conservation significance, particularly within intact grassland, wetland, seepage, riparian, rocky, and forest-associated habitats.

Figure 3-5 Map illustrating the screened area and the locations of the expected species.

Table 3-1 List of potential species and their likelihood of occurring onsite.

Species	Redlist Status	Family	Likelihood of Occurrence	Notes
<i>Alepidea cordifolia</i>	Endangered A2bd	Apiaceae	High	Confirmed by this study
<i>Aloe hlangupies</i>	Vulnerable B1ab(iii)	Asphodelaceae	High	Confirmed by this study
<i>Aloe kniphofioides</i>	Near Threatened B1ab(iii)	Asphodelaceae	High	Species presence in the study area was confirmed through observations by others.
<i>Aloe modesta</i>	Vulnerable B1ab(iii)+2ab(iii)	Asphodelaceae	High	Species presence in the study area was confirmed through observations by others.
<i>Aspidoglossum demissum</i>	Vulnerable D2	Apocynaceae	High	Species presence in the study area was confirmed through observations by others.
<i>Bowiea volubilis</i> subsp. <i>Volubilis</i>	Vulnerable A2ad	Hyacinthaceae	Medium	No recent nearby observations but potential to occur based on habitat requirements
<i>Brachystelma gerrardii</i>	Endangered C2a(i)	Apocynaceae	High	Confirmed by this study
<i>Brachystelma remotum</i> " <i>Ceropegia remota</i> "	#N/A	#N/A	High	Species presence in the study area was confirmed through observations by others.
<i>Clivia miniata</i> var. <i>miniata</i>	Vulnerable A2abcd	Amaryllidaceae	Low	Unlikely to occur onsite due to historical records. The site and forests are likely too cold for this species.
<i>Curtisia dentata</i>	Near Threatened A2d	Curtisiaceae	High	Confirmed by this study
<i>Dierama erectum</i>	Endangered B1ab(ii,iii,iv,v)	Iridaceae	High	Confirmed by this study
<i>Dioscorea sylvatica</i>	Vulnerable A2cd	Dioscoreaceae	High	Confirmed by this study

<i>Disa maculomarronina</i>	Near Threatened B2ab(iii)	Orchidaceae	High	Confirmed by this study
<i>Dracosciadium italae</i>	Vulnerable B1ab(i,ii,iii)	Apiaceae	High	Confirmed by this study
<i>Gerbera aurantiaca</i>	Endangered A2ac	Asteraceae	High	Confirmed by this study
<i>Gladiolus paludosus</i>	Vulnerable B1ab(i,ii,iii,iv,v)+2ab(i,ii,iii,iv,v)	Iridaceae	High	Likely to occur and lots of potential habitat onsite but not observed within the KPE.
<i>Habenaria culveri</i>	Rare	Orchidaceae	Medium-High	Potential habitat onsite but not recorded within the nearby area
<i>Indigofera hybrida</i>	Vulnerable D2	Fabaceae	Medium	Potential habitat onsite but not recorded within the nearby area
<i>Melanospermum italae</i>	Vulnerable B1ab(iii)	Scrophulariaceae	High	Likely to occur and lots of potential habitat onsite but not observed within the KPE.
<i>Merwillia plumbea</i>	Near Threatened A2bd	Hyacinthaceae	High	Confirmed by this study
<i>Nerine gracilis</i>	Vulnerable B1ab(ii,iii,v)	Amaryllidaceae	Medium	Potential habitat onsite but not recorded within the nearby area and the edge of the species distribution
<i>Nerine platypetala</i>	Vulnerable B1ab(i,ii,iii,iv,v)	Amaryllidaceae	Medium	Recorded closer to Wakkerstroom, however there is ideal habitat and therefore a medium potential to occur onsite.
<i>Protea parvula</i>	Near Threatened A2c; B1b(iii,v)+2b(ii,iv)	Proteaceae	High	Species presence in the study area was confirmed through observations by others.
<i>Satyrium microrrhynchum</i>	Rare	Orchidaceae	High	Ideal habitat onsite but not recorded within the nearby area
<i>ocotea kenyensis</i>	Vulnerable D1	Lauraceae	low-Medium	Potential habitat onsite but not previously recorded from the nearby region.
<i>ocotea bullata</i>	Endangered A2bd	Lauraceae	Medium	Ideal habitat onsite but very few historical observations from the nearby region giving the overall likelihood a medium.
<i>Xerophyta vallispongolana</i>	Vulnerable D2	Velloziaceae	Medium	Recorded further east of the study area, however there is ideal habitat and therefore a medium potential to occur onsite.
<i>Aspidoglossum xanthosphaerum</i>	Vulnerable D2	Apocynaceae	High	Recorded closer to Wakkerstroom, however there is ideal habitat and therefore a medium potential to occur onsite.
<i>Searsia harveyi</i>	Near Threatened D2	Anacardiaceae	Low-Medium	Recorded further south of the study area, however there is some potential habitat and therefore a low-medium potential to occur onsite. It is very likely too cold onsite during winter for this species to occur.
<i>Encephalartos natalensis</i>	Vulnerable A2acd	Zamiaceae	Low-Medium	Recorded further east and south of the study area, however there is some potential habitat and therefore a low-medium potential to occur onsite. It is very likely too cold onsite during winter for this species to occur.
<i>Searsia dracomontana</i>	Near Threatened B1ab(iii)+2ab(iii)	Anacardiaceae	Medium-High	Ideal habitat onsite but very few recent records of this species onsite or in the nearby region, therefore a medium to high likelihood.

4 Results

4.1 Habitats

The study area supports a range of habitat types that together reflect the environmental heterogeneity of the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment Figure 4-1. From a botanical perspective, these habitats differ in terms of substrate, soil moisture, topographic position, disturbance history, and vegetation structure, all of which influence species composition and local floristic patterns. The habitat mosaic recorded onsite includes intact and secondary grasslands, wetland and riparian systems, forest patches, alluvial areas, rocky grassland on different geological substrates, and areas affected by alien plant invasion. The habitats, their sizes and percentages are listed in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1 *Habitat percentage within the PAOI.*

Habitat	Area (ha)	% cover
Dolerite Grasslands	2360.6	32.9
Sandstone Grasslands	1461.0	20.4
Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland	731.2	10.2
Alluvial Grasslands	710.8	9.9
Alien Vegetation	700.0	9.8
Wetlands/Riparian vegetation	577.2	8.0
Northern Afromontane Forest	503.9	7.0
Secondary Grasslands	132.6	1.8
Total	7177.3	100.0

This variation in habitat type is reflected in the floristic composition of the site and helps explain the occurrence of species of conservation importance across the study area. Certain habitats, particularly Dolerite Grasslands, Wetland/Riparian Vegetation, and Northern Afromontane Forest, supported a notable number of threatened, rare, protected, or range-extended species, while other habitats contribute additional floristic diversity and ecological complexity. The following habitat descriptions provide a botanical overview of each mapped habitat type recorded during the assessment.

Figure 4-1 Map illustrating the habitat types associated with the PAOI

4.1.1 Alien Vegetation and Modified Areas

Alien Vegetation and Modified Areas include portions of the study area where the natural plant community has been substantially altered by invasive alien species, past disturbance, or land

transformation. This category includes alien-dominated vegetation, old lands, secondary or disturbed areas, roadsides, and active crop fields, as well as other modified parts of the landscape where indigenous vegetation has been reduced, fragmented, or replaced. In some places these areas may still retain remnant indigenous species, but overall they are generally characterised by lower floristic integrity and a simplified vegetation structure compared to the more intact natural habitats.

From a botanical perspective, these areas are typically associated with reduced indigenous species richness and an increased dominance of invasive or disturbance-tolerant species, including taxa such as *Acacia mearnsii*, *Acacia dealbata*, and other alien woody or herbaceous plants. Active crop fields and other transformed areas contribute further to this category by replacing natural vegetation entirely and creating additional edge effects that can promote invasion into adjacent habitats. These areas are important primarily from a management perspective, as they can act as sources of ongoing disturbance and alien spread into neighbouring grassland, wetland, riparian, and forest habitats. Effective management should therefore focus on preventing further expansion of alien species, limiting edge effects from cultivated and otherwise modified areas, and promoting the recovery or rehabilitation of natural vegetation where feasible

4.1.2 Alluvial Grasslands

Alluvial Grasslands occur on deeper, more fertile soils associated with drainage lines, floodplains, valley bottoms, and depositional areas. Within the study area, these habitats are likely to support a relatively productive grassland layer, often with taller and denser growth than the surrounding upland slopes. Botanically, these areas are expected to include a mixture of mesic grassland species, moisture-associated forbs, and locally important ecotonal species linked to alluvial or seasonally moist conditions. Because of their position within the landscape, alluvial grasslands often function as transitional habitat between open grassland and wetland or riparian systems, and may support species associated with seepage, stream margins, or floodplain edges. They can therefore contribute disproportionately to local botanical diversity, especially where they remain relatively intact and are not heavily transformed, overgrazed, or invaded by alien species.

4.1.3 Dolerite Grasslands

Dolerite Grasslands form one of the most important habitat types in the study area from a botanical perspective. These grasslands are generally associated with doleritic geology, shallow to moderately deep soils, rocky slopes, upland plains, and exposed grassland ridges. Floristically, they support a species-rich grassland flora with a strong forb and geophytic component, and many of the species of conservation importance recorded during the assessment were associated with this habitat. SCCs such as *Aloe hlangapies*, *Brachystelma gerrardii*, *Dierama erectum*, *Dracosciadium italaе*, *Gerbera aurantiaca*, *Leobordea difformis*, and *Lotononis amajubica* were recorded from Dolerite Grasslands, together with a number of rare and range-extended taxa including *Aspidoglossum dissimile*, *Helichrysum spodiophyllum*, *Heteromma krookii*, *Buddleja loricata*, *Crassula peploides*, *Helichrysum confertum*, *Helichrysum tenuifolium*, *Holothrix scopularia*, *Indigofera rubroglandulosa*, *Romulea macowanii*, and *Zaluzianskya pulvinata*.

This habitat is therefore particularly important for the conservation of the site's montane grassland flora. Botanically, Dolerite Grasslands are likely characterised by species-rich assemblages of grasses such as *Themeda triandra*, *Tristachya leucothrix*, and *Hyparrhenia hirta*, together with a high diversity of perennial forbs, bulbs, orchids, and habitat specialists associated with rocky ground, seepage areas, drainage features, and shallow soils. Their importance within the study area is reinforced by the number of threatened, rare, and range-extended species they support.

4.1.4 Northern Afromontane Forest

Northern Afromontane Forest occurs as small, sheltered forest patches associated with moist slopes, drainage lines, kloofs, scarps, and protected ravines. From a botanical perspective, this habitat is structurally and floristically distinct from the surrounding grassland matrix and supports a specialised woody and understorey flora. Characteristic canopy and tall tree species include *Podocarpus latifolius*, *Afrocarpus falcatus*, *Pittosporum viridiflorum*, *Olinia emarginata*, *Halleria lucida*, and *Celtis africana*, while the understorey may include shrubs, ferns, herbs, and forest-margin species.

Within the study area, this habitat supported several conservation-important taxa, including *Curtisia dentata*, *Dioscorea sylvatica*, and *Prunus africana*, as well as the nationally protected tree species *Afrocarpus falcatus*, *Pittosporum viridiflorum*, and *Podocarpus latifolius*. The rare species *Scolopia oreophila* and the decreasing species *Ilex mitis* var. *mitis* were also associated with this habitat. Northern Afromontane Forest is therefore highly significant botanically, despite often occurring as relatively small patches, and contributes substantially to habitat heterogeneity, floristic diversity, and the occurrence of forest-associated conservation-important flora.

4.1.5 Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland

Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland is a tall, closed, species-rich grassland type associated with moderately undulating terrain, deeper soils, and relatively moist conditions. Botanically, it is characterised by a strong forb component and a dense grass layer dominated by species such as *Tristachya leucothrix*, *Themeda triandra*, and *Hyparrhenia hirta*. Compared to shorter montane grasslands, this habitat generally has a more robust and often taller physiognomy, especially in areas with limited disturbance and favourable soil moisture.

Within the study area, Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland contributes to the broader highland grassland mosaic and is important for supporting grassland forbs, geophytes, and ecotonal taxa. Although only a limited number of conservation-important records were directly linked to this habitat in the final cleaned dataset, it remains botanically important because of its floristic richness, its links to the regional grassland flora, and its capacity to support SCCs and expected species that may not have been detected during the survey. This habitat is also vulnerable to degradation through heavy grazing, afforestation, inappropriate burning, and alien invasion, all of which can reduce forb diversity and alter grassland structure.

Within the PAOI, most of this grassland community has been transformed by extensive afforestation, leaving only fragmented remnant patches. Despite their limited extent, these remnants remain of high conservation importance, as they preserve intact portions of an endangered ecosystem.

4.1.6 Sandstone Grasslands

Sandstone Grasslands occur on sandstone-derived soils and rocky substrates and are likely to be associated with more skeletal soils, exposed rock sheets, and specific edaphic conditions that differ from surrounding doleritic habitats. From a botanical perspective, these grasslands may support a somewhat distinct flora, including species adapted to shallow, rocky, and often nutrient-poor conditions. Within the study area, the range-extended *Moraea ardesiaca* was recorded from Sandstone Grasslands, indicating that this habitat contributes unique floristic elements to the overall vegetation mosaic.

Although this habitat appears to have been limited in extent relative to Dolerite Grasslands, its botanical significance lies in the fact that sandstone-derived substrates can create specialised habitat conditions that support locally restricted or less commonly recorded species. These areas should therefore be regarded as floristically important, particularly where rock sheets, seeps, or rocky drainage features increase microhabitat diversity.

4.1.7 Secondary Grasslands

Secondary Grasslands refer to grassland areas that have been modified by historical disturbance, such as previous cultivation, clearing, localised degradation, or other forms of transformation, but which have subsequently reverted to a grass-dominated state. From a botanical perspective, these areas are typically distinguishable from primary or less-disturbed grasslands by altered species composition, lower floristic integrity, reduced abundance of sensitive or specialist taxa, and a higher representation of disturbance-tolerant species. They may nonetheless retain some indigenous grassland elements and can contribute to connectivity or serve as partial recovery habitat within the broader landscape.

Within the study area, secondary grasslands are likely to support a subset of the regional grassland flora, but generally with lower conservation value than intact Dolerite Grasslands or Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland. However, depending on the age of disturbance and degree of recovery, these habitats may still provide opportunities for rehabilitation and may support some common indigenous species. Their management should aim to promote natural recovery, reduce ongoing disturbance, and limit the spread of alien or invasive species.

4.1.8 Wetland/Riparian Vegetation

Wetland/Riparian Vegetation is one of the most botanically important habitats within the study area due to its role in supporting moisture-dependent and habitat-specialist flora. These habitats include wetlands, seeps, drainage lines, streambanks, wet grassland, and riparian margins, all of which provide ecological conditions distinct from the surrounding upland grassland matrix. Botanically, they support a specialised flora adapted to permanently or seasonally moist soils, fluctuating water availability, and sheltered drainage features.

Within the study area, several important species were associated with this habitat, including SCCs such as *Alepidea attenuata*, *Alepidea cordifolia*, *Bowkeria citrina*, and *Disa maculomarronina*, as well as rare species such as *Disa rhodantha* and *Euryops gilfillanii*. *Disa stricta*, a range-extended species, was also associated with wetland and riparian habitat. These habitats are therefore highly significant for the conservation of moisture-dependent taxa and contribute substantially to the overall botanical diversity of the site. From a management perspective, wetland and riparian areas are also particularly sensitive to trampling, drainage, overgrazing, erosion, alien plant invasion, and altered hydrological conditions, and should be regarded as priority habitats for protection and careful management.

4.2 Overview of the Survey Results

A total of 1 358 botanical observations were recorded during the field surveys, representing 797 unique species from 157 plant families. This reflects a floristically rich study area with a strong representation of montane grassland, wetland, riparian, rocky, and forest-associated flora. The overall richness recorded during the survey is consistent with the high habitat heterogeneity of the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment and highlights the botanical importance of the surveyed farms.

The flora recorded during the study was strongly dominated by species-rich grassland and forb-associated families. The most species-rich families recorded were:

- Asteraceae – 100 species
- Orchidaceae – 43 species
- Fabaceae – 42 species
- Poaceae – 35 species
- Asparagaceae – 31 species
- Iridaceae – 30 species

These families are characteristic of diverse high-altitude grassland systems, particularly those with a strong herbaceous and geophytic component. In terms of overall observation frequency, Asteraceae was also the most frequently recorded family, followed by Orchidaceae, Iridaceae, Asparagaceae, Fabaceae, and Lamiaceae. This pattern reflects the high diversity of forbs and geophytes within the study area, especially in the more intact grassland habitats.

At farm level, the greatest number of observations and highest species richness were recorded from Donkerhoek 172/2 and Groothoek 171/2. These farms contributed strongly to the overall floristic richness of the study area and appear to contain some of the most diverse habitat mosaics within the survey area. The farm-level results can be summarised as follows:

- Donkerhoek 172/2 – 241 observations; 207 species
- Groothoek 171/2 – 232 observations; 194 species
- Groothoek 171/3 – 161 observations; 144 species
- Groothoek 171/4 – 154 observations; 134 species
- Groothoek 171/R – 149 observations; 137 species
- Groothoek 171/1 – 133 observations; 127 species
- Roodewal 190/1 – 88 observations; 83 species
- Donkerhoek 172/4 – 28 observations; 27 species

At habitat level, Dolerite Grasslands supported the greatest number of observations and the highest species richness, followed by Northern Afromontane Forest and Sandstone Grasslands. Wetlands/Riparian Vegetation also supported a substantial number of observations and species, while Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland and Alluvial Grasslands contributed additional habitat-specific

diversity. Alien Vegetation supported the lowest richness, as would be expected in more disturbed and transformed areas. The habitat-level patterns were as follows:

- Dolerite Grasslands – 412 observations; 316 species
- Northern Afromontane Forest – 286 observations; 196 species
- Sandstone Grasslands – 212 observations; 175 species
- Wetlands/Riparian Vegetation – 146 observations; 127 species
- Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland – 86 observations; 81 species
- Alluvial Grasslands – 38 observations; 37 species
- Alien Vegetation – 6 observations; 6 species

These results indicate that the more intact natural habitats, particularly Dolerite Grasslands, Northern Afromontane Forest, and Sandstone Grasslands, are the main drivers of botanical richness within the study area. The high number of species recorded from Dolerite Grasslands is especially significant and supports the broader finding that this habitat is one of the most important from both a floristic and conservation perspective. Similarly, the species richness recorded in forest and wetland-associated habitats shows that these smaller or more localised habitat types contribute substantially to the overall diversity of the site.

4.3 Conservation Important Species

A number of plant species of conservation importance were recorded within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment during the assessment. To make the findings easier to present and discuss, these species were grouped into separate categories based on their conservation status and overall botanical significance. This also helps to show that not all-important species fall into the same type of concern, as some are threatened, some are locally rare, some are protected by legislation, and others are important because they represent unusual or unexpected records for the area.

For the purposes of this report, the conservation-important species recorded within the KPE were separated into the following categories: Species of Conservation Concern (SCCs), Rare species, species whose range has been extended, Potential New Species and New Species, species which are Decreasing, and Nationally Protected Tree Species. This structure provides a practical way of discussing the different types of botanical significance recorded during the survey and helps to highlight the range of conservation values associated with the study area.

Below in Figure 4-2 all conservation important species can be seen and a heat or density map showing which areas the highest concentration of species was found. The areas of yellow and blue have the highest concentration of species.

Figure 4-2 Map illustrating the location of the conservation important species and which areas have the highest concentrations associated with the PAOI.

4.3.1 Species of Conservation Concern (SCCs)

A total of 14 SCCs were recorded during the assessment. These species include Endangered, Vulnerable, Near Threatened, and Rare taxa associated with wetlands, riparian zones, Dolerite Grasslands, and Northern Afromontane Forest. The presence of these taxa confirms the high botanical significance of the study area and highlights the importance of conserving intact habitat across the site.

4.3.1.1 *Alepidea attenuata*

Alepidea attenuata is listed as Near Threatened under criterion B2ab(i,ii,iii,iv,v). This species is rare but widespread and is associated with a restricted and threatened habitat type that is declining due to damming, drainage for crop cultivation, trampling by cattle, fragmentation associated with pine plantations, and alien plant invasion. Its area of occupancy is less than 800 km² and it is known from approximately 7–12 locations. Within the broader region it occurs in the Limpopo escarpment, Witwatersrand, Mpumalanga highlands, Swaziland Highveld, northern Free State, and northern KwaZulu-Natal Highveld. It grows in wetlands and grassland up to 2 200 m and was recorded in

	Wetlands/Riparian Vegetation within the study area.
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4.3.1.2 *Alepidea cordifolia* (Heartleaf Ministar)

Alepidea cordifolia is listed as Endangered under criterion A2bd. The population is estimated to have declined by at least 50% over the last three generations due primarily to persistent harvesting pressure for the medicinal plant trade, together with habitat loss associated with afforestation and crop cultivation. This species is highly sought after medicinally and has been exploited throughout its range both within and outside South Africa. It is not endemic to South Africa and is widespread across the eastern highveld of Mpumalanga, the eastern Free State, north-western KwaZulu-Natal, Lesotho margins, Swaziland, the Eastern Highlands of Zimbabwe, and the Chimanimani Mountains of Mozambique. It typically occurs on forest margins, west- and south-facing mountain slopes, and near drainage lines or islands within wetlands. Within the study area it was recorded from Wetlands/Riparian Vegetation and Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.1.3 *Aloe hlangapies*

Aloe hlangapies is listed as Vulnerable under criterion B1ab(iii). This species has a restricted distribution range and the population has been severely fragmented as a result of habitat loss to timber plantations and agriculture. Ongoing habitat loss and degradation continue to drive decline. It is endemic to a small area in southern Mpumalanga and northern KwaZulu-Natal, extending into south-western Eswatini. The species occurs most frequently on rocky outcrops in grassland, as well as on road cuttings, and likely also occurred historically in open grassland near drainage lines and seeps before much of this habitat was lost or degraded. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.1.4 *Bowkeria citrina* (Yellow Shellflower)

Bowkeria citrina is listed as Rare. It is a range-restricted South African endemic with an extent of occurrence of approximately 277 km² and is regarded as a habitat specialist, although no specific threats are currently known. The species is distributed in southern Mpumalanga and northern KwaZulu-Natal between Groenvlei, Wakkerstroom, and Lüneburg. It occurs on forest margins and cliff edges on cool slopes between 1 400 and 1 800 m. Within the study area it was recorded from Wetlands/Riparian Vegetation and Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.1.5 *Brachystelma gerrardii*

Brachystelma gerrardii is listed as Endangered under criterion C2a(i). Although relatively widespread, this species is exceptionally rare, with subpopulations usually consisting of fewer than 10 mature individuals. It is currently known from about 20 locations, with the total population conservatively estimated at fewer than 2 500 mature individuals. Decline is linked primarily to habitat destruction in KwaZulu-Natal, where most known subpopulations occur, and is further associated with livestock overgrazing, inappropriate fire regimes, cultivation, afforestation, alien plant invasion, and possible harvesting for food. It occurs in open grassland between 400 and 1 800 m and was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands within the study area.

4.3.1.6 *Curtisia dentata* (Assegai Tree)

Curtisia dentata is listed as Near Threatened under criterion A2d. This species has been exploited across much of its South African range due to timber extraction and bark harvesting for the traditional medicine trade. Population decline over the last 120 years is estimated to exceed 20%, and further decline is anticipated as harvesting pressure continues. Recent harvesting pressure has reportedly shifted into Mpumalanga as the species has become scarcer in KwaZulu-Natal. *Curtisia dentata* occurs from the Cape Peninsula to the Zimbabwe-Mozambique highlands and is associated with evergreen forest from the coast to 1 800 m. Within the study area it was recorded in Northern Afromontane Forest.

4.3.1.7 *Dierama erectum*

Dierama erectum is listed as Endangered under criterion B1ab(ii,iii,iv,v). It is known from 11 small and severely fragmented subpopulations at eight locations within a very small extent of occurrence. Most remaining subpopulations occur in grassland fragments and are declining due to overgrazing. This South African endemic occurs between northern KwaZulu-Natal and southern Mpumalanga, between Ngome and Lüneburg, and is associated with wet mistbelt grassland on dolerite along streams. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.1.8 *Dioscorea sylvatica* (Forest Elephantsfoot)

Dioscorea sylvatica is listed as Vulnerable under criterion A2cd. This species underwent a major population decline during the mid-twentieth century due to indiscriminate commercial harvesting for diosgenin, and exploitation for the medicinal plant trade continues to limit recovery. The total decline is estimated to exceed 30% over the past 90 years. It is widespread in South Africa and also occurs in Eswatini, Zimbabwe, and Zambia. The species grows in wooded and relatively mesic habitats, including moister bushveld, coastal bush, and wooded mountain kloofs. Within the study area it was recorded in Northern Afromontane Forest.

4.3.1.9 *Disa maculomarronina* (Maroonspot Disa)

Disa maculomarronina is listed as Near Threatened under criterion B2ab(iii). It is a habitat specialist associated with swamps and montane grassland on the edges of Black Reef Quartzite between 1 500 and 1 700 m. Its area of occupancy is extremely small and it is known from fewer than 10 locations, although it may occur at up to 10–15 locations. It is threatened by afforestation, trampling, and harvesting by tourists. This South African endemic is known from Wakkerstroom and the Mpumalanga Escarpment around Graskop. Within the study area it was recorded in Wetlands/Riparian Vegetation.

4.3.1.10 *Dracosciadium italae*

Dracosciadium italae is listed as Vulnerable under criterion B1ab(i,ii,iii). This South African endemic has a limited extent of occurrence and is known from fewer than 10 locations. Much of its habitat has been transformed by forestry plantations, and remaining habitat is threatened by ongoing degradation, particularly severe overgrazing. The species occurs on hilltops in the Vryheid-Ngome district of northern KwaZulu-Natal and in the Wakkerstroom area of southern Mpumalanga. It is associated with montane and mistbelt grassland on rock outcrops with dolerite soils between 1 200 and 1 600 m. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.1.11 *Gerbera aurantiaca* (Hilton daisy)

Gerbera aurantiaca is listed as Endangered under criterion A2ac. This is a mistbelt grassland endemic whose habitat has been heavily transformed by commercial forestry, crop and pasture cultivation, and urban development. It is a long-lived clonal species with poor recruitment and low seed viability, and is therefore unlikely to recover readily from historical habitat loss. The species is distributed in the KwaZulu-Natal Midlands, Carolina, and Badplaas and occurs in mistbelt grassland on well-drained doleritic soils. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.1.12 *Leobordea difformis*

Leobordea difformis is listed as Vulnerable under criterion D2. It is known from a single location, where part of the habitat has already been transformed to forestry plantations, and further plantation expansion remains a potential threat. This South African endemic is known from Piet Retief and occurs in grassland habitat. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.1.13 *Lotononis amajubica*

Lotononis amajubica is listed as Rare. It is a South African endemic and a habitat specialist of well-drained, high-altitude grassland between 1 600 and 1 800 m. Although it may be locally common where suitable habitat persists, it remains significant due to its restricted distribution across the high mountain peaks of southern Mpumalanga, north-western KwaZulu-Natal, and the eastern Free State. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.1.14 *Prunus africana* (Red stinkwood)

Prunus africana is listed as Vulnerable under criteria A4acd and C1+2a(i). The bark of this species is widely used in traditional medicine and the species has been overexploited across much of its range. In South Africa, it has already undergone substantial decline, particularly in KwaZulu-Natal, where it is locally extinct in more than half the forests it previously occupied. Population reductions are expected to continue, and South African populations are thought to be small and declining. The species is widespread across Africa and, in South Africa, occurs from Mpumalanga through KwaZulu-Natal to the Knysna forests. It grows in evergreen coastal, mistbelt, and afro-montane forests up to 2 100 m. Within the study area it was recorded from Northern Afro-montane Forest.

4.3.2 Rare Species

A total of seven rare species were recorded during the assessment. Although these species are not all formally listed as threatened, they remain important from a botanical perspective due to their local rarity, restricted distributions, habitat specificity, or because they are seldom encountered in the broader landscape. In several cases, these records are also noteworthy because they represent unusual recent observations, including first observations on iNaturalist or the first confirmed collection in many decades. As with the SCCs, the presence of these species adds to the overall conservation value of the site and highlights the importance of retaining intact habitat across the KPE.

4.3.2.1 *Aspidoglossum dissimile*

Aspidoglossum dissimile is currently listed as Least Concern, but is treated as rare within the context of this assessment. It is associated with high-altitude grassland, particularly Sub-Escarpment Grassland, and is known from elevations of approximately 2 000–2 225 m. The species is very scattered in its distribution and is known from the north-eastern Eastern Cape, the Transvaal/KwaZulu-Natal border, and the eastern Transvaal. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands. Although it is not currently regarded as threatened at a national level, its scattered distribution and rarity make it a noteworthy component of the local flora.

4.3.2.2 *Disa rhodantha* (Swamp Disa)

Disa rhodantha is listed as Least Concern, but is recorded as a rare species within the study area. It occurs in swamps, on streambanks, in seeps, and in wet grassland, and is associated with wetland and moist grassland habitats including Drakensberg Grassland and Sub-Escarpment Grassland. Although it is widely distributed, populations are locally isolated. Provincial records include KwaZulu-Natal, Limpopo, and Mpumalanga. Within the study area it was recorded from Wetlands/Riparian Vegetation, which is consistent with its preference for wet and sensitive habitat.

4.3.2.3 *Euryops gilfillanii*

Euryops gilfillanii is listed as Least Concern and is a well-defined species distinguished by its acaulescent habit, narrow leaves, and long, slender peduncles arising from a woolly crown. It has been recorded from Gauteng and Mpumalanga, where it occurs in open grassland and rock crevices, but appears to favour shallow, moist, sandy soils on mountain plateaus and sheet rock. In suitable habitat it may form large colonies. Within the study area it was recorded from the Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.2.4 *Helichrysum spodiophyllum*

Helichrysum spodiophyllum is listed as Least Concern, but was treated as rare within the context of this assessment. It forms large woody mats on rock outcrops and rock sheets in grassland, rooting in rock crevices and sprawling across adjacent rock surfaces. The species is recorded from the Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, and Mpumalanga, and has historically been documented from a relatively broad but scattered range including Lydenburg, the Mbabane district, the low Drakensberg along the KwaZulu-Natal–Mpumalanga border, Itala, Ngome, Ceza, Mt Gilboa, Lion’s River, and then disjunctly in the Eastern Cape. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands. This observation is notable as it represents the first record of the species on iNaturalist, even though the species is historically fairly widely distributed.

4.3.2.5 *Heteromma krookii* (Smooth Skintdaisy)

Heteromma krookii is listed as Least Concern, but was treated as a rare species within the context of this assessment. It occurs in mesic grassland, especially in drainage lines on steep mountain slopes, rocky stream gullies, and the steep stony margins of forest patches and *Leucosidea* scrub, where it may form dense stands. Its known distribution extends along the Drakensberg from Normandien Pass near Newcastle in KwaZulu-Natal to the mountains around Harrismith in the Free State, including nearby Van Reenen and Royal Natal National Park. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands. This record is especially noteworthy as it represents the first observation of the species on iNaturalist.

4.3.2.6 *Scolopia oreophila* (Pongola Redpear)

Scolopia oreophila is listed as Least Concern, but is considered rare due to its narrow distribution and limited number of known subpopulations. It occurs along the margins of streambank scrub and forest, as well as at the edges of forest and on rocky outcrops at high altitude. It is known only from the Utrecht District of KwaZulu-Natal and has a relatively small extent of occurrence and area of occupancy. The species is threatened by fire, firewood harvesting, and local habitat loss to afforestation, although the extent of these impacts remains uncertain. Within the study area it was recorded from Northern Afromontane Forest, which is in keeping with its preference for forest margin habitat.

4.3.2.7 *Senecio eminens*

Senecio eminens is listed as Data Deficient – Insufficient Information and was treated as rare in this assessment. Much of its grassland habitat has been transformed and it may be threatened, but too little is currently known about its full distribution, habitat requirements, or present population status to determine its conservation status with certainty. The species was last collected in 1949, making the current record particularly important as the first collection of the species since that time. The specimen was collected and confirmed by taxonomist Marinda Koekemoer. The species is known from Mpumalanga, with a range extending from Piet Retief to Mbabane in Eswatini, and within the study area it was recorded within the Dolerite Grasslands.

4.3.3 Range-Extended Species

A total of 10 species recorded during the assessment were identified as range-extended species. These records are important because they improve current understanding of species distributions within the broader KwaMandlangampisi and Wakkerstroom landscape and show that the site supports habitat suitable for taxa not previously known, or not previously confirmed, from this part of Mpumalanga. In some cases, these records represent slight southern or northern extensions of known distributions, while in others they mark the first known record for Mpumalanga. Together, these findings add further botanical significance to the study area and highlight the value of detailed field survey work in intact montane grassland and associated habitats.

4.3.3.1 *Buddleja loricata* (Mountain Sagewood)

Buddleja loricata represents the first known record of this species for Mpumalanga and marks a slight northern extension of its known distribution. The species is typically found on the slopes of high mountains, usually at altitudes above 1 676 m, where it occurs amongst boulders or in damp, sheltered gullies. Its presence within the study area indicates the availability of suitable high-altitude montane habitat and adds to the phytogeographical significance of the site.

4.3.3.2 *Crassula peploides*

Crassula peploides is still poorly known, with relatively little information available on its full distribution and ecology. It has previously been recorded mainly from the Drakensberg region, and the present record marks a slight northern extension of its known range. This finding is of botanical interest as it suggests that the species may be more widespread than currently documented, or that suitable habitat persists further north than previously recognised.

4.3.3.3 *Disa stricta* (Floodplain Disa)

Disa stricta is known as an occasional and locally common species in the mountains of the Eastern Cape, Lesotho, and KwaZulu-Natal, but had not previously been recorded from Mpumalanga. The present record therefore represents a notable range extension into the province. The species is associated with grassy slopes and damp floodplains, and its occurrence within the study area further emphasises the importance of mesic grassland and wetland-associated habitats.

4.3.3.4 *Helichrysum confertum* (Crowded Everlasting)

Helichrysum confertum was previously known only from the high Drakensberg, and the present record represents a northern range extension into Mpumalanga where the species had not previously been documented. This finding is significant in a regional context and suggests floristic links between the study area and the higher elevation Drakensberg flora.

4.3.3.5 *Helichrysum tenuifolium*

Helichrysum tenuifolium was previously recorded only from the Drakensberg and the current record represents a northern range extension into Mpumalanga, where it had not previously been documented. The species grows in colonies in rocky gullies, along stream sides, in boulder beds, amongst rock outcrops, or as part of fynbos-like communities. It has been recorded from the Natal Drakensberg between Cathedral Peak and the upper Polela area, west of Himeville. Its presence within the study area indicates the occurrence of specialised rocky montane habitat capable of supporting regionally significant range-edge populations.

4.3.3.6 *Holothrix scopularia* (Brush Hair Orchid)

Holothrix scopularia is associated with rocky grassland at high altitudes and has been recorded from Drakensberg Grassland, Sub-Escarpment Grassland, Dry Highveld Grassland, and Sub-Escarpment Savanna. Its known distribution includes the Drakensberg of the Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, the Free State, and Lesotho, with an additional record from Barberton in Mpumalanga. The present record is noteworthy in the context of the study area as it extends the known occurrence of the species within the broader region and reinforces the floristic links between the high-altitude grasslands of KwaMandlangampisi and the greater Drakensberg system.

4.3.3.7 *Indigofera rubroglandulosa* (Redgland Indigo)

Indigofera rubroglandulosa was previously known from Natal and the Transkei, and the present record represents a northern range extension. This is an important phytogeographical record, as it demonstrates that the species extends further north than previously documented. Its occurrence within the study area adds to the conservation importance of the site and contributes to a better understanding of species distribution patterns in the region.

4.3.3.8 *Moraea ardesiaca*

Moraea ardesiaca was previously considered restricted to the northern Drakensberg of KwaZulu-Natal and the adjacent Free State, from Van Reenen to Lotheni, with an outlying population in the vicinity of Utrecht. It occurs in moist grassland in stream valleys, along streams, and in seeps amongst rocks. The current record therefore represents a meaningful extension of the known range of the species into the study area and further highlights the importance of moist montane grassland and seep habitats within the KPE.

4.3.3.9 *Romulea macowanii* (Grassveld Froetang)

Romulea macowanii has previously been recorded from the Eastern Cape and Free State. It is a high-altitude species associated with moist open grassland and rock sheets, and its broader range includes Lesotho and the south-eastern central plateau and adjacent mountains, extending westwards to the Sneeuberge and Murraysburg, and south to Grahamstown, with an isolated record near Fraserburg. The present record is therefore significant as it extends the known range of the species into Mpumalanga and indicates that the study area supports suitable high-altitude grassland habitat for this taxon.

4.3.3.10 *Zaluzianskya pulvinata* (Cushion Drumsticks)

Zaluzianskya pulvinata is known from the Belfast and Barberton districts in the south-eastern Transvaal, through KwaZulu-Natal, the mountains of the north-eastern Free State, Lesotho, the mountains of Transkei, and the Cape Drakensberg and Witteberg near Barkly East and Lady Grey. It favours bare stony places, often in and around rock sheets or rock outcrops. Although the species is known from parts of the broader region, its record within the study area remains noteworthy in the context of the survey and contributes to the documentation of species distribution within the KPE landscape.

4.3.4 Potential new species and new species

A small number of taxa recorded during the assessment were separated into a category for potential new species and new species. These records are botanically important because they may represent taxa that are difficult to identify with confidence in the field, taxa requiring further taxonomic work, or species that may prove to be new or otherwise noteworthy once specialist confirmation has been completed. Although these records should be treated with caution until formally resolved, they add to the overall significance of the survey and suggest that the flora of the area is still not fully understood. No follow up work has been planned, however collection of these specimens for further identification is encouraged.

4.3.4.1 *Brownleea commitans*

An observation potentially identified as *Brownleea commitans* was recorded from the project area. This identification hasn't been confirmed and may be a new species if not confirmed as *Brownleea commitans*. *Brownleea commitans* is a recently described species with very little information. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands on top of eMhlongamvula. At this stage, the record should be regarded as noteworthy but provisional, pending further taxonomic verification. Even so, the occurrence of this taxon within the study area is important, as it may represent a significant addition to the known flora of the area.

4.3.4.2 *Cyphia* spp.

A taxon identified only to genus level as *Cyphia* was recorded and classified as a potential new species. It was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands and Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland. The inability to confidently assign the record to species level suggests that the specimen is taxonomically difficult, unusual, or in need of additional specialist review. As such, it is treated as a taxon of interest pending further confirmation.

4.3.4.3 *Euryops* spp.

A taxon identified only as *Euryops* spp. was recorded and placed in the potential new species category. As with the *Cyphia* record, the identification could not be resolved confidently to species level, and the taxon therefore remains of interest pending further taxonomic investigation. The species grows in high altitude sheet rock wetlands and flowered from December to February.

4.3.4.4 *Phymaspermum c.f. comptonii* (Swati Shepdaisy)

A species currently identified as *Phymaspermum comptonii* was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands within the study area. However, as the original type specimen for *P. comptonii* is not available online, it is difficult to determine with confidence whether the recorded plants are conspecific with *P. comptonii* or may represent a potentially undescribed species within the genus. The record should therefore be interpreted with caution pending the collection of suitable material and verification by a taxonomic specialist against the type. Despite this uncertainty, the finding remains botanically noteworthy and suggests that parts of the flora within the study area may still be under-documented.

4.3.5 Decreasing Species

Two species recorded during the assessment were separated into a decreasing category, namely *Ilex mitis* and *Protea subvestita*. Although both are currently listed as Least Concern, they are considered noteworthy because available information indicates that their populations are declining in parts of their range. Their inclusion in this category helps to highlight species that may not yet qualify as threatened, but which still warrant attention from a management perspective due to ongoing pressures affecting their long-term persistence.

4.3.5.1 *Ilex mitis* (Cape Holly)

Ilex mitis is currently listed as Least Concern but has experienced notable declines in parts of its South African range due to bark stripping for the medicinal plant trade. It is widespread from the Western Cape northwards to Ethiopia and also occurs in Madagascar. The species is typically associated with rivers and streams in forest and thicket, although it may also occur in more open situations, from sea level to inland mountain slopes. Within the study area it was recorded from Northern Afromontane Forest. While it is not currently regarded as threatened nationally, its declining trend in parts of its range makes it a species of concern in the context of long-term habitat management and resource use.

4.3.5.2 *Protea subvestita* (Waterlily Sugarbush)

Protea subvestita is also currently listed as Least Concern but is considered to be decreasing. It is a widespread Drakensberg Escarpment endemic occurring from near Wakkerstroom southwards to the Eastern Cape, with former occurrences also recorded in Lesotho. Although still relatively widespread, the species is declining due to harvesting for firewood and overly frequent fires. It is associated with infrequently burnt habitats, often occurring along gullies, scarps, and forest margins. Occasional fire is required for recruitment, but mature plants are killed by fire, with only seeds surviving in fire-resistant inflorescences. Within the study area it was recorded from Dolerite Grasslands. Its occurrence is significant as it reflects the importance of maintaining appropriate fire regimes within the grassland landscape.

4.3.6 Nationally Protected Tree Species

Three nationally protected tree species were recorded during the assessment, namely *Afrocarpus falcatus*, *Pittosporum viridiflorum*, and *Podocarpus latifolius*. All three species were recorded from Northern Afromontane Forest habitat, which highlights the ecological sensitivity and conservation importance of the forest patches present within the study area. The occurrence of these protected tree species has direct management implications, particularly in relation to the avoidance of disturbance or loss of indigenous forest habitat.

4.3.6.1 *Afrocarpus falcatus* (Outeniqua Yellowwood)

Afrocarpus falcatus is a nationally protected tree species and was recorded from Northern Afromontane Forest within the study area. Its presence confirms the importance of intact forest habitat and contributes to the conservation significance of the site. As a protected tree species, it is legally protected and should be considered a sensitivity feature in any future land use or management planning.

4.3.6.2 *Pittosporum viridiflorum* (Kersuurboom)

Pittosporum viridiflorum is also a nationally protected tree species recorded from Northern Afromontane Forest. The presence of this species further emphasises the value of the indigenous forest component of the study area. As with the other protected tree taxa, its occurrence supports the need for continued protection of remaining forest patches and associated ecotones.

4.3.6.3 *Podocarpus latifolius* (Real Yellowwood)

Podocarpus latifolius is a nationally protected tree species recorded from Northern Afromontane Forest within the study area. This species is an important component of indigenous afromontane forest systems and contributes to the conservation importance of the forest habitat present. Its presence reinforces the need to avoid disturbance to indigenous forest and to maintain the ecological integrity of these habitats over the long term

5 Discussion

5.1 General Management Observation Per Farm

A farm-level management review was undertaken to provide a practical overview of ecological condition, current pressures, and management priorities across the study area. Although the farms form part of the broader KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment, each property differs in terms of habitat composition, veld condition, grazing pressure, alien plant invasion, fire history, and overall management context. For this reason, a farm-specific discussion is necessary to reflect the variation observed across the landscape and to ensure that management recommendations are relevant to the conditions present on each property.

The sections below provide a general management observation for each farm based on field observations made during the survey. These observations consider the main habitat types present, overall veld condition, successional status, grazing pressure, fire regime where evident, alien plant invasion, and other key factors influencing ecological condition. The intention is not to provide a detailed grazing audit or formal land capability assessment, but rather to summarise the main ecological patterns and management considerations relevant to the long-term conservation and sustainable use of each farm.

5.1.1 Groothoek 171/4 (452 ha)

Groothoek 171/4 is one of the most unique and botanically diverse farms within the study area. The farm supports a highly heterogeneous habitat mosaic comprising Dolerite Grasslands, Sandstone Grasslands, Wetland/Riparian Vegetation, and Northern Afromontane Forest. Of particular significance are the sheet rock habitats and high-altitude wetlands associated with the upper slopes and summit area of the Madlangampisiberg, which reaches approximately 2 270 m.a.s.l. These habitats are highly distinctive in the local context and contribute substantially to the ecological and botanical value of the property.

The farm was assessed as being in very good overall veld condition, with a dominant climax successional state and a rich, diverse herbaceous layer present across much of the property. Grazing pressure was considered low, with very little evidence of significant utilisation observed at the time of survey. This suggests that the current grazing management system is functioning effectively and should be maintained. Alien plant invasion was recorded as absent or negligible, which further supports the conclusion that the farm remains in a relatively intact ecological state.

The current fire regime was considered appropriate and well managed, and this should continue in line with the broader burning guidelines for the area. As with grazing, fire management should remain sensitive to habitat type, particularly in and around the high-altitude wetlands, rocky summit habitats, forest patches, and other ecotonal areas that are likely to be especially sensitive to disturbance. These habitats are important not only because of their ecological distinctiveness, but also because they contribute disproportionately to the farm's botanical diversity and conservation value.

Overall, Groothoek 171/4 is a farm of particularly high ecological and botanical significance. Management should focus on maintaining the current low grazing pressure, retaining the favourable veld condition and climax composition, continuing the existing fire management approach, and ensuring the long-term protection of the summit wetlands, sheet rock habitats, and forest-associated areas that make this property especially important within the broader study area.

5.1.2 Groothoek 171/3 (384 ha)

Groothoek 171/3 supports a diverse habitat mosaic comprising Alien Vegetation, Alluvial Grasslands, Dolerite Grasslands, Northern Afromontane Forest, Sandstone Grasslands, and Wetland/Riparian Vegetation. From a botanical perspective, this variety of habitats contributes to the overall ecological richness of the farm and provides a range of niches for grassland, wetland, riparian, and forest-

associated species. The presence of both upland grassland and forested habitats, together with alluvial and wetland features, suggests that the farm is likely to support a relatively diverse flora and should be managed with the aim of maintaining this habitat heterogeneity.

Overall veld condition on Groothoek 171/3 was assessed as good, although grazing pressure appears to be high and the dominant successional state of the veld was noted as sub-climax. This suggests that while the farm still retains good ecological function and species composition, grazing pressure may already be influencing structure and preventing portions of the veld from expressing a more fully climax condition. Alien plant invasion was noted as low, which is positive, but continued monitoring and early intervention are recommended to prevent future spread, particularly in wetter areas, drainage features, and disturbed margins.

A further management consideration for Groothoek 171/3 is the risk of pine spread from adjacent properties. Although no major pine infestation was recorded on the farm during the survey, neighbouring seed sources may result in gradual recruitment into natural habitat over time. Regular monitoring is therefore recommended so that any establishing pine individuals can be removed before they become established and begin spreading further.

No clear evidence of recent burning or a defined fire pattern was observed during the assessment. In the absence of obvious fire indicators, future burning should follow the broader ecological burning guidelines applicable to the area, with care taken to avoid inappropriate frequency or seasonality, especially in sensitive habitats such as wetlands, riparian zones, forest margins, and rocky slopes. Forest patches on the farm were noted to be expanding, which is an important management consideration. While forest patches contribute positively to habitat diversity, their expansion into surrounding grassland should be monitored where this may lead to the loss of open grassland habitat of botanical importance.

Overall, Groothoek 171/3 appears to be a botanically attractive and diverse farm with good veld condition and a strong habitat mosaic. Ongoing management should focus on maintaining current habitat diversity, limiting excessive grazing pressure where necessary, monitoring the expansion of forest patches, controlling alien plants while infestations remain low, and applying an ecologically appropriate fire regime to support long-term grassland and wetland condition.

5.1.3 Groothoek 171/2 (1258 ha)

Groothoek 171/2 supports the full range of vegetation and habitat types recorded within the study area, including Alien Vegetation, Alluvial Grasslands, Dolerite Grasslands, Northern Afromontane Forest, Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland, Sandstone Grasslands, Secondary Grasslands, and Wetland/Riparian Vegetation. The presence of all mapped vegetation types on a single farm makes this property particularly important from a habitat diversity perspective. Botanically, this level of habitat heterogeneity provides a wide range of niches for grassland, wetland, forest, and disturbance-associated species, and contributes substantially to the overall ecological value of the farm.

Overall veld condition on Groothoek 171/2 was assessed as fair, with the dominant successional state of the veld considered to be sub-climax. Grazing pressure was noted as high, suggesting that livestock utilisation is influencing veld structure and likely limiting the recovery or persistence of a more intact climax grassland condition in parts of the farm. Although alien plant invasion was assessed as low overall, a poplar infestation was noted and should be treated, particularly where it may affect drainage lines, wetlands, or alluvial areas.

Although *Acacia* infestations were noted as a concern within the broader study area, no major riparian infestations were observed on Groothoek 171/2 at the time of survey, suggesting that these species are currently relatively well controlled along the river system on this farm. This is a positive management outcome and should be maintained through continued monitoring and early follow-up clearing of any new recruits. However, there remains an ongoing risk of reinvasion through downstream seed dispersal

from upstream infestations, particularly from Groothoek 171/1. This means that even where local control is effective, long-term success will depend on coordinated management across connected properties within the catchment.

No clear evidence of a recent or defined fire regime was observed during the assessment. In the absence of clear fire indicators, burning should be managed carefully in line with the broader ecological burning guidelines for the area, with emphasis on appropriate frequency and the avoidance of unnecessary impacts to wetlands, riparian zones, and forest margins. Particular attention should also be given to grazing-related disturbance in sensitive areas. Cattle were noted to be contributing to wetland erosion in places, although this was not considered severe at the time of assessment. This suggests that wetland condition remains recoverable, but would benefit from improved grazing distribution and more careful management of livestock movement and congregation.

Poor rotation of feeding or lick sites was also noted, and this is likely contributing to localised overutilisation and disturbance. Improved placement and rotation of these attractants would help reduce concentrated pressure on specific parts of the farm and may assist in improving veld condition over time. It was also noted that forest patches are not expanding, which suggests that woody encroachment or forest spread is not currently a major concern on this farm. In addition, very little invasion by *Pteridium aquilinum* was observed, which is a positive feature from a grassland management perspective.

Overall, Groothoek 171/2 is a highly diverse farm with considerable ecological value, but one that would benefit from more careful grazing and disturbance management. Future management should focus on reducing grazing pressure where possible, improving the rotation of feeding and lick sites, limiting further wetland erosion by livestock, controlling poplar infestation, and maintaining an ecologically appropriate fire regime. With improved management of these pressures, the farm has good potential to recover toward a stronger climax grassland condition while retaining its high habitat diversity.

5.1.4 Groothoek 171/R (1191 ha)

Groothoek 171/R supports a diverse range of habitats, including Alien Vegetation, Alluvial Grasslands, Dolerite Grasslands, Northern Afromontane Forest, Sandstone Grasslands, Secondary Grasslands, and Wetland/Riparian Vegetation. This range of habitat types contributes to the ecological complexity of the farm and provides a variety of niches for grassland, wetland, riparian, and forest-associated flora. However, despite this habitat diversity, the farm appears to be experiencing a relatively high level of management pressure that is influencing overall veld condition.

The overall veld condition of Groothoek 171/R was assessed as fair, with the dominant successional status considered to be sub-climax. Grazing pressure was noted as high, indicating that current utilisation levels are likely limiting veld recovery and contributing to the suppression of more desirable climax species in parts of the farm. The fire regime could not be clearly determined at the time of assessment, and this uncertainty further highlights the need for a more structured and clearly implemented veld management approach.

Alien plant invasion on Groothoek 171/R was assessed as severe, with a particularly serious infestation of *Pteridium aquilinum* observed. Bracken fern expansion is often associated with disturbance, altered fire regimes, and selective grazing pressure, and its presence at this level is a significant management concern. If left unmanaged, it is likely to continue displacing more desirable grassland species and reducing the overall ecological and grazing value of affected areas.

Forest patches on the farm were noted to be expanding rapidly. While forest habitat is itself important, uncontrolled expansion into surrounding grassland can result in the loss of open grassland habitat of high botanical value. This suggests that portions of the farm may be experiencing a shift in vegetation structure, potentially linked to fire exclusion, grazing patterns, or broader changes in disturbance dynamics. Monitoring and active management of this process will therefore be important in maintaining the balance between forest and grassland habitats.

The current large camp system may also be contributing to uneven grazing distribution and prolonged grazing pressure in certain areas. Based on field observations, a smaller camp system with higher short-term grazing pressure and longer rest periods is likely to be more effective. A rotational grazing system of this nature would help improve veld recovery, reduce selective overutilisation, and support more resilient grassland structure over time. Depending on management objectives and stocking strategy, the farm may also benefit from reconsideration of animal numbers in relation to grazing duration and rest periods. This doesn't necessarily imply less animals.

Overall, Groothoek 171/R is a diverse farm with considerable ecological value, but one that is clearly under pressure from grazing, bracken fern invasion, and changing vegetation dynamics. Management should focus on reducing the long-term impact of grazing through improved camp rotation, addressing the severe bracken infestation as a priority, monitoring and managing woody thickening at the grassland–forest ecotone, and implementing a more clearly defined fire regime that supports grassland persistence and recovery.

5.1.5 Groothoek 171/1 (1647 ha)

Groothoek 171/1 supports a diverse range of habitats, including Alien Vegetation, Alluvial Grasslands, Dolerite Grasslands, Northern Afromontane Forest, Sandstone Grasslands, Secondary Grasslands, and Wetland/Riparian Vegetation. This habitat diversity contributes to the overall ecological complexity of the farm and provides suitable conditions for a wide range of grassland, wetland, riparian, and forest-associated plant species. However, despite this diversity, the farm is showing signs of ecological pressure and requires targeted management to prevent further decline in habitat quality.

The overall veld condition of Groothoek 171/1 was assessed as fair, with the dominant successional status considered to be sub-climax. Grazing pressure was recorded as moderate, indicating that while grazing is not currently excessive across the entire farm, it is still likely contributing to the suppression of a more intact climax grassland condition in parts of the property. No clear evidence of a recent or well-defined fire regime was observed during the assessment, and this uncertainty suggests that future fire management should be more clearly planned and implemented in line with ecological burning guidelines for the area.

Alien plant invasion is a major concern on Groothoek 171/1 and was assessed as severe. In particular, there is a severe infestation of black wattle (*Acacia mearnsii*) and silver wattle (*Acacia dealbata*), especially within forest and riparian habitat types. These species pose a substantial threat to indigenous vegetation by displacing native flora, altering habitat structure, and affecting water availability and ecosystem function. In addition, *Pteridium aquilinum* infestation was also identified as a significant issue on the farm. As with other disturbed grassland systems, bracken invasion is likely to be linked to disturbance patterns, fire history, and veld condition, and should be considered a priority for active management.

The severe infestation of *Acacia mearnsii* and *Acacia dealbata* on Groothoek 171/1 is of concern not only at farm level, but also in relation to downstream spread and broader aquatic impacts. Because these invasions occur within riparian and drainage-associated habitats, there is a significant risk that seed may be washed downstream during flow events and establish on lower-lying farms, creating a continuing reinvasion risk for connected properties such as Groothoek 171/2 and other downstream farms. In addition, dense riparian stands of these species may affect aquatic ecosystem functioning by contributing large volumes of fine leaf litter and woody material to stream systems, altering instream habitat structure and potentially reducing the suitability of breeding and spawning habitat for fish and other aquatic organisms.

Overall, Groothoek 171/1 remains an ecologically diverse farm, but one under considerable pressure from invasive plant encroachment. Management should focus on the control and progressive removal of *Acacia mearnsii*, *Acacia dealbata*, and *Pteridium aquilinum*, particularly in forest and riparian habitats where these invasions are most severe. At the same time, grazing and fire management should be

refined to support recovery of the grassland component and prevent further degradation. With appropriate intervention, the farm has the potential to improve in condition while retaining its important habitat diversity.

5.1.6 Donkerhoek 172/2 (688 ha)

Donkerhoek 172/2 supports a range of habitats including Alien Vegetation, Dolerite Grasslands, Northern Afromontane Forest, Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland, and Wetland/Riparian Vegetation. This combination of habitats contributes to the ecological and botanical value of the farm and provides suitable conditions for both grassland and forest-associated flora, as well as species linked to wetter parts of the landscape. The presence of multiple natural habitat types suggests that the farm remains an important component of the broader habitat mosaic within the study area.

Overall veld condition on Donkerhoek 172/2 was assessed as good, with a mixed or variable successional state across the farm. Grazing pressure was considered moderate, which suggests that the farm is currently being utilised, but not to the point of causing obvious widespread degradation. The fire regime was regarded as appropriate and well managed, which is an important positive feature and should be maintained, as appropriate burning is critical for sustaining grassland condition and limiting woody and invasive encroachment.

Alien plant invasion was recorded as localised only, although some localised infestations of wattle and *Pteridium aquilinum* were observed and should be addressed before they expand further. A particular management concern for this farm is the risk of future alien plant spread from Donkerhoek 172/4, where a wattle and blue gum plantation or related business is present. This creates an ongoing source of propagules and increases the likelihood of further invasion into adjacent natural habitat if not actively monitored and managed.

Overall management of Donkerhoek 172/2 appears to be good. No severe signs of erosion or forest encroachment were noted, which suggests that current land management is broadly maintaining ecological stability. Going forward, management should focus on retaining the current good veld condition, continuing the existing fire management approach, and implementing early control of localised wattle and bracken infestations. Particular attention should also be given to monitoring the farm boundary and vulnerable habitat edges for further alien spread originating from neighbouring land use activities.

5.1.7 Donkerhoek 172/4 (688 ha)

Donkerhoek 172/4 supports Alien Vegetation, Dolerite Grasslands, Northern Afromontane Forest, and Wetland/Riparian Vegetation. Much of the farm appears to be associated with the more acidic expression of Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland, likely linked to granitic soils, and this is important from a botanical perspective as it influences species composition and veld response. Although natural habitat remains present on the farm, overall condition is variable and the farm is subject to several significant pressures that distinguish it from the other properties in the study area.

The overall veld condition was assessed as variable across the farm, with the dominant successional state generally considered to be sub-climax. Grazing pressure was noted as low, and in some areas may be absent or insufficient to stimulate healthy veld dynamics. From a grassland management perspective, this is important, as the veld requires a well-managed grazing system to maintain structure, promote species turnover, and prevent stagnation or retrogression. In the natural areas, the species assemblage was broadly what would be expected for the habitat types present, although generally at a sub-climax level.

Alien plant invasion on Donkerhoek 172/4 was assessed as severe, which is not surprising given the presence of an existing pine, wattle, and blue gum plantation business on the farm. From a botanical perspective, this land use presents several challenges, including ongoing alien plant encroachment, edge effects, disturbance associated with machinery and logging, and broader degradation of adjacent

natural habitat. These pressures are likely contributing to veld retrogression and reducing the ecological integrity of the remaining natural areas. Plantation-related impacts may also increase the risk of invasion and degradation on neighbouring properties, making this farm important in the wider management context of the study area.

The fire regime on the farm was recorded as unknown. However, it is clear that fire management is complicated by the close proximity of natural habitat to plantation areas. Despite this, a well-managed burning programme is still encouraged in order to stimulate grassland condition and maintain the ecological functioning of the veld, provided this can be done safely and in a controlled manner. Careful planning will be needed to balance fire management objectives with plantation risk and the protection of sensitive habitats such as forest patches and riparian areas.

Overall, Donkerhoek 172/4 remains botanically important due to the natural habitats still present, but it is under considerable pressure from plantation-related impacts and severe alien invasion. Management should focus on containing and reducing alien plant spread, minimising edge and disturbance effects associated with plantation operations, reintroducing or improving an appropriate grazing system where absent, and implementing a carefully planned burning programme to support grassland recovery and veld function.

5.1.8 Roodewal 190/1 (868 ha)

Roodewal 190/1 supports a range of habitats including Alien Vegetation, Dolerite Grasslands, Northern Afromontane Forest, Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland, Wetland/Riparian Vegetation, and Secondary Grasslands. From a botanical perspective, the farm remains important because it still retains remnant patches of intact natural vegetation within a broader landscape that has been substantially altered. In particular, the remaining areas of Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland and associated riparian and forest habitats contribute significantly to the ecological value of the property. The Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland is a threatened grassland listed as endangered and therefore the remnant patches have significant ecological value.

Overall veld condition on Roodewal 190/1 was assessed as fair, with the dominant successional status considered to be sub-climax. Grazing pressure was described as variable across the farm, suggesting that utilisation is uneven and may differ considerably between the more intact areas and the more transformed sections of the property. No clear evidence of a recent or defined fire regime was observed during the assessment, and future fire management should therefore be approached carefully and in line with the broader ecological burning guidelines for the area.

Alien plant invasion is the main management concern on Roodewal 190/1 and was assessed as severe. In particular, extensive invasion by silver wattle was noted, especially along the main Ntombe River tributary. This is likely having a substantial impact on riparian and adjacent habitat quality, with negative implications for indigenous species composition, habitat structure, and water-related ecosystem processes. The farm also contains large old fields or secondary grasslands, as well as extensive active crop fields, which further contribute to habitat transformation and fragmentation across the property.

Despite these pressures, Roodewal 190/1 still contains remnant intact patches of high botanical value. Of particular note were the impressive blooms of *Watsonia watsonoides* recorded in remnant patches of Paulpietersburg Moist Grassland, where several thousand flowers were observed. This highlights the importance of the remaining intact grassland fragments and demonstrates that even within a transformed landscape, the farm continues to support botanically significant habitat.

Overall, Roodewal 190/1 is a farm where the main management priority should be the control of alien plant invasion, especially along riparian systems and around remaining natural habitat. Management should also focus on retaining and protecting the remnant intact grassland and forest patches, improving the condition of secondary grasslands where possible, and limiting further degradation

associated with transformation and uneven grazing pressure. With targeted intervention, the remaining natural areas on the farm could continue to play an important role in conserving local botanical diversity.

5.2 General Management Recommendations

The habitats present within the study area should be managed in a manner that maintains ecological function, supports floristic diversity, and protects sensitive habitat features such as wetlands, riparian areas, rocky grasslands, and forest margins. In general, management should aim to retain habitat heterogeneity across the landscape, limit chronic disturbance, and apply grazing, burning, and alien plant control in a structured and adaptive way. Given the high botanical value of the site and the number of conservation-important species recorded, management should be precautionary and should avoid uniform treatment of all habitats, as different habitat types respond differently to disturbance and recovery processes.

A central principle of long-term management should be regular monitoring to assess veld condition and guide adaptive management. This is particularly important in a landscape such as the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment, where habitat condition, species composition, grazing response, fire effects, and alien plant invasion can vary considerably between farms and habitat types. Monitoring should include regular assessment of basal cover, grass species composition, herbaceous diversity, evidence of erosion, wetland and riparian condition, alien plant spread, and changes in woody cover or woody thickening at the grassland–forest ecotone. Monitoring should be used to determine whether veld condition is improving towards a climax state, remaining in a stable sub-climax condition, or regressing towards a more disturbed or pioneer-dominated condition. Without this feedback, it is difficult to know whether current management is maintaining, improving, or degrading the veld.

5.2.1 Grazing management

Across all habitat types, grazing should be managed conservatively and rotationally, with sufficient rest built into the system to allow recovery of the herbaceous layer and to maintain species diversity. A full growing season of rest should be provided to portions of the farm each year where possible, and stocking levels should remain within conservative ecological limits, especially in high-altitude or species-rich grasslands. Repeated grazing of the same camps in the same season should be avoided, as this can reduce plant vigour, suppress desirable perennial species, and promote disturbance-associated or invasive taxa. Selective overuse of sensitive areas such as rocky refugia, wetlands, riparian margins, and steep slopes should be prevented wherever possible.

From a grazing management perspective, there are broadly two schools of thought that may be considered appropriate within the study area, depending on the farm context, infrastructure, labour availability, management objectives, and what is practical for the landowner or manager.

The first is a light rotational grazing system, in which livestock are moved through camps in a way that avoids repeated use of the same areas and allows for regular recovery of the veld. Under this approach, grazing pressure remains relatively moderate and camps are rested for meaningful periods during the growing season. This system is often easier to implement where camp sizes are larger, infrastructure is more limited, or the current grazing system is already functioning reasonably well. If properly applied, light rotational grazing can help maintain basal cover, reduce selective overgrazing, and support the persistence of desirable grassland species, particularly where veld condition is already fair to good.

The second is a high-density, short-duration grazing system with long rest periods. Under this model, livestock are concentrated at high density in smaller camps for short periods, followed by sufficiently long rest periods to allow the veld to recover fully before being grazed again. When carefully implemented, this approach can improve grazing distribution, reduce chronic selective utilisation, promote more even use of the veld, and create conditions that may favour recovery of grassland structure and species composition. It can also help reduce the patch grazing often associated with large-camp systems. Importantly, short-duration, high-intensity systems with long rest periods may have the potential to achieve high returns for the farm owner while simultaneously improving veld condition. However, these systems are management-intensive and depend on appropriate camp infrastructure, timing, stocking density, and disciplined rest periods. If poorly implemented, they can also lead to localised degradation, particularly around water points, feeding sites, and sensitive habitats.

Both systems can be viable, and the most suitable approach will ultimately depend on what is practical and achievable for the individual farm owner or manager. Factors such as camp layout, labour availability, livestock type, habitat sensitivity, wetland extent, slope, erosion risk, and management goals all need to be taken into account. Regardless of the system selected, the key principle is that grazing should not be continuous, rest must be built into the system, and veld response should be monitored regularly so that management can be adjusted if necessary.

5.2.2 Fire management

Fire management should be applied in a way that maintains biodiversity, supports veld condition, and retains habitat heterogeneity rather than simplifying the vegetation. A patch mosaic burning approach is recommended, whereby relatively small sections are burned at different times so that the landscape contains patches in different post-fire stages. This promotes structural and floristic diversity, reduces the risk of repeated uniform disturbance, and provides refugia for species that are sensitive to frequent or extensive burning such as reptiles.

In practice, the timing of burning should be guided not only by operational convenience, but also by veld condition, fuel load, moribund material, rainfall, and habitat sensitivity. Burning is generally most appropriate where there is sufficient accumulated biomass to carry a safe and effective fire, and where moribund material has built up to the point that it is suppressing new growth, reducing grassland vigour, or limiting access by grazers. In productive mesic grassland, such as those found in the PAOI, this often means that a burn interval of approximately two to five years may be suitable, depending on local conditions and management objectives. More frequent burning may be appropriate in some heavily moribund or underutilised patches, while less frequent burning may be preferable in lower-fuel or more sensitive areas. Burning should not be applied on a fixed calendar basis alone, but rather in response to veld condition and fuel accumulation.

As a general guide, burns should be considered where there is enough standing dry material to carry a patchy but effective fire and where old moribund grass has accumulated to the extent that it is reducing light penetration, suppressing herbaceous diversity, or contributing to stagnant veld condition. Conversely, areas with low fuel loads, insufficient resting, recent burns, or already heavily grazed grassland should generally not be burned, as fire under these conditions may further weaken the veld and increase erosion risk. Burning should therefore be preceded by a practical assessment of fuel continuity, grass vigour, litter accumulation, and recent grazing history.

With regard to seasonality, cooler burns undertaken before the peak dry season are often preferable where the aim is to reduce fuel safely, manage moribund material, and limit the risk of damaging hot fires. In many cases, late summer to early autumn burns can be useful under controlled conditions, particularly where there is still some soil and plant moisture present. Spring burns can also be used in, especially where the objective is to stimulate fresh growth, but they can be more intense and should be used cautiously in sensitive habitats or where fuel loads are high, as these late burns have the potential to burn too hot and damage the roots of the plants being burned. Another good general rule of thumb is to avoid burning during the growing season, as this also damages the grass sward, which is then potentially further damaged by the early spring grazing. Repeated burning at the same time of year should be avoided, as this can favour certain species over others and reduce overall heterogeneity. A varied but well-planned seasonal approach is generally preferable.

Overall, as much as burning is a routine annual practice, fire should be treated as a management tool that is applied selectively and in response to veld condition. The key indicators for burning should include accumulated biomass, moribund material, declining grass vigour, reduced grazing accessibility, and the need to maintain a mosaic of veld structure across the farm. If applied in this way, fire can help maintain productive and species-rich grassland while reducing the risk of veld stagnation, woody encroachment, and excessive fuel build-up.

5.2.3 Wetland and riparian protection

Wetland and riparian habitats require particular care, as they are highly sensitive to trampling, erosion, channel incision, alien invasion, and poorly timed burning. These habitats should be integrated into broader grazing and fire planning, but management should remain cautious and responsive to site condition. Livestock should be excluded or pressure substantially reduced in wetland areas during wet periods or where signs of erosion and trampling are evident. Wetlands should be burned only under cool, moist conditions and not all at once, ideally at intervals that allow recovery of the vegetation and the retention of refugia. Buffer strips of unburnt or lightly grazed vegetation should be maintained along wetland and riparian margins to help protect hydrological function and water quality.

5.2.4 Alien plant control

Alien plant control should be an ongoing management priority across the study area, particularly in riparian areas, old lands, disturbed patches, forest margins, and modified areas. Control should be systematic and sustained over time, with priority given to outlying infestations, expanding patches, and species known to be particularly aggressive invaders, such as wattles, poplars, pines, blue gums, and bracken fern where relevant. Follow-up control is essential, as initial clearing without continued treatment is unlikely to be effective. Cleared areas should be monitored and, where necessary, stabilised or rehabilitated to prevent reinvasion or erosion. Mechanical removal should be used carefully, especially on slopes or near drainage lines, to avoid creating additional disturbance.

5.2.5 Erosion prevention

To reduce erosion risk across the site, management should aim to maintain good basal cover and avoid exposing bare soil through overgrazing, poorly timed burning, or concentrated livestock pressure. Roads, tracks, watering points, and feeding or lick sites should be monitored and managed to reduce concentrated runoff and localised degradation. Steep slopes, seepage areas, and drainage features are especially vulnerable and should be protected from repeated disturbance. Where erosion is already present, early intervention should be implemented through physical stabilisation measures and the recovery of vegetative cover.

5.2.6 Maintaining herbaceous diversity

Maintaining herbaceous diversity is a key management objective, particularly in the species-rich montane grassland habitats that characterise much of the study area. This requires the maintenance of habitat heterogeneity, a varied grazing and fire regime, and the protection of less disturbed patches that can act as refugia for sensitive species. Repeated heavy grazing, overly frequent burning, or prolonged absence of disturbance in appropriate habitats can all reduce floristic diversity. Monitoring of veld condition and species composition should therefore be undertaken regularly so that management can be adapted where early signs of decline or simplification are observed.

5.2.7 Forest patches and margins

Forest patches and forest margins must be monitored for protection. The forest edge is a highly sensitive habitat feature. While the forest core is important, the forest edge is often the most critical management zone, as this is where many of the main pressures act most strongly. Forest margins are the interface between closed forest and surrounding grassland, wetland, riparian, or transformed areas, and are often the first places where alien plant invasion, grazing disturbance, inappropriate fire, and edge-related drying or structural change become evident. For this reason, forest-edge management should receive specific attention rather than being treated as part of general grassland management.

Alien plant invasion is one of the main threats to these edge habitats. Species such as *Acacia mearnsii*, *Acacia dealbata*, *Populus* spp., *Eucalyptus* spp., *Solanum mauritianum*, and in some cases *Pinus* spp. tend to establish first along forest margins, drainage lines, and disturbed ecotones before spreading further into surrounding habitat. These species alter light levels, suppress indigenous understorey and edge flora, change moisture conditions, and can eventually transform both the forest edge and adjacent natural vegetation. Forest edges should therefore be inspected regularly and alien plants should be

removed early, before dense infestations become established. Clearing should start with isolated plants, young recruits, and expanding edge infestations, followed by consistent follow-up control.

Grazing pressure along forest margins should also be carefully managed. Livestock often concentrate along ecotones, especially where shade, shelter, or water is available, and this can lead to trampling, soil disturbance, suppression of edge flora, and local erosion. Repeated grazing along forest boundaries can also simplify the transition zone between forest and grassland, making these areas more vulnerable to invasion. As far as possible, livestock access to sensitive forest margins, especially where slopes are steep or soils are soft, should be reduced or managed seasonally to prevent chronic disturbance.

Fire management near forest patches should be cautious and deliberate. Hot fires along forest edges can damage woody vegetation, open the forest margin, and make these zones more vulnerable to alien invasion and desiccation. At the same time, complete fire exclusion from the surrounding grassland may allow forest patches or woody species to expand into areas of important open grassland habitat. The objective should therefore be to maintain a stable and ecologically functional forest-grassland boundary. Burning adjacent grassland in a patchy, cool, and controlled manner is generally preferable to intense fires that run directly into forest margins. Unburnt buffer strips or naturally moist edge zones should be retained where possible.

From a practical management perspective, forest-edge zones should be monitored regularly for signs of invasion, erosion, grazing pressure, canopy opening, and shifts in the boundary between forest and surrounding grassland. Management should aim to maintain the integrity of the forest patch while also retaining the natural ecotone between forest and adjacent habitat. This means controlling alien plants early, limiting concentrated livestock disturbance, avoiding destructive fire at the margin, and preventing unnecessary clearing, logging, or disturbance within or immediately adjacent to the forest edge. In this study area, these transition zones are particularly important because they support a number of forest-associated species, rare taxa, and protected trees, and play a major role in the overall habitat heterogeneity and botanical value of the landscape.

5.2.7.1 Woody thickening at the grassland–forest ecotone

Although *Leucosidea sericea* (Ouhout) is a well-known woody pioneer in these montane grassland systems and does contribute to local scrub thickening, the observed reduction in open grassland extent cannot be attributed to this species alone. In the study area, increased woody cover is more appropriately interpreted as a broader process of woody encroachment linked to changes in the ecological drivers that maintain grassland, particularly fire and grazing. This process may include local forest-margin advance, scrub expansion, and increased woody dominance in suitable microsites. Management should therefore focus on maintaining appropriate ecological drivers rather than treating the issue as a single-species invasion problem. Where this species has become a problem within the surrounding region it is mainly due to a change in the ecological drivers such as fire, grazing or climatic changes.

Forest margins will expand or contract over time depending on the prevailing management regime and climatic conditions. In this regard, changes in the extent of woody cover should not automatically be interpreted as true forest expansion, but rather as a dynamic response to factors such as fire frequency, grazing pressure, local disturbance, moisture availability, and topographic shelter. Where forest-edge expansion is associated with the development of new *Pteridium aquilinum* (bracken fern) stands and ouhout thickets adjacent to existing forest patches, management intervention may be needed in some areas. In more heavily affected areas, mechanical or chemical control may be appropriate to limit further encroachment into open grassland habitat. However, these interventions should be supported by an ecologically appropriate burning regime, as increased fire frequency may help limit further woody and bracken encroachment and promote more natural grassland processes.

5.3 Alien invasive plant management

There are large areas of Alien Invasive plant species occurring in the PAOI (Figure 5-1). Alien invasive plant control should be treated as an ongoing management priority across the study area, especially in wetlands, riparian areas, forest margins, old lands, disturbed grassland, roadsides, and other modified areas. These habitats are generally the most prone to invasion and, if not managed, often act as source areas for further spread into intact natural vegetation. In terms of both CARA and NEM:BA, landowners are legally responsible for controlling invasive plants on their properties, and this should form part of the broader farm management programme.

The main alien invasive species of concern within the study area are *Acacia dealbata*, *Acacia mearnsii*, *Eucalyptus* spp., *Pinus pinaster*, *Populus* spp., *Solanum mauritianum*, and *Lantana camara*. These species reduce indigenous plant diversity, suppress natural grassland and wetland vegetation, increase competition for water, and often lower the grazing value of affected areas. In riparian zones and wetlands they can also alter drainage, destabilise banks, and displace indigenous species of conservation importance. *Lantana camara* is of particular concern in grazing areas as it is toxic to cattle.

Control should be approached practically and systematically. In most cases, complete eradication is unlikely once infestations are well established, and the aim should rather be long-term control through repeated clearing and follow-up. A once-off clearing operation is rarely effective, as seeds, coppice regrowth, and rootstock regeneration will usually result in reinfestation. The most effective approach is therefore to prioritise infestations strategically. Initial efforts should focus on outlier plants, recently established invasions, and infestations in sensitive habitats such as wetlands, drainage lines, riparian corridors, forest margins, and intact grassland. Larger dense infestations can then be tackled progressively as part of a longer-term programme.

In general, seedlings and small shrubs can be treated using foliar herbicide application, provided that suitable products are used and spraying is done carefully to avoid damage to surrounding indigenous vegetation. Larger shrubs and trees are best controlled using a cut-stump treatment. This involves cutting stems low to the ground and applying a registered systemic herbicide to the cut surface immediately after felling. This method is particularly important for woody invaders such as *Acacia mearnsii*, *Acacia dealbata*, *Populus* spp., *Eucalyptus* spp., and *Pinus* spp. Where regrowth occurs after clearing, it should be allowed to resprout to a workable size and then treated again. Follow-up control is essential and should be budgeted for over several years.

Particular care is needed when dealing with species that coppice or resprout strongly, especially *Acacia mearnsii*. If cut too high above the ground, or if herbicide is not applied properly, these species can recover quickly from basal buds. For this reason, stems should be cut as low as possible and treated thoroughly. All seed-bearing material should be removed or destroyed where feasible, especially in or near watercourses. In less sensitive sites, cleared material without seed can be used for brush-packing on eroded areas if appropriate.

Chemical control should only be undertaken by properly trained personnel using registered herbicides and the correct application methods. Herbicides should be mixed according to label instructions and applied during periods of active growth, generally in spring and summer. Spraying should be avoided when rain is expected or where wind may cause drift onto indigenous species. Workers must wear appropriate protective clothing, and all herbicide use should comply with legal requirements.

The invasive indigenous fern *Pteridium aquilinum* should be managed separately from the alien invasive species. Although indigenous, it can become highly aggressive in disturbed grassland and can dominate large areas, suppressing grasses and forbs and reducing both conservation and grazing value. A phased control approach is recommended. Dense stands can first be treated chemically using an appropriate herbicide such as Asulam or another registered alternative. Dead fronds should then be removed and regrowth spot-treated. Thereafter, the site should be managed to encourage the recovery of indigenous grassland species through improved grazing and fire management. In many cases, annual follow-up treatment will be needed until the stand is under control.

Alien plant control should always be linked to broader habitat management. If the drivers of invasion remain in place, such as chronic disturbance, poorly managed grazing, bare ground, altered fire regimes, or unmanaged plantation edges, reinvasion is likely. Cleared areas should therefore be monitored regularly and rehabilitated where necessary to reduce erosion and improve the recovery of indigenous vegetation. In practical terms, the most effective long-term strategy is early detection, rapid response to new infestations, careful follow-up, and integration of alien clearing with broader veld and habitat management.

Figure 5-1 Map illustrating the Locations of Alien Invasive Plants.

6 Conclusion

The botanical assessment of the eight farms within the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment confirmed that the study area supports a diverse and ecologically important flora within a broader landscape of high conservation significance. A total of 797 plant species from 157 families were recorded, reflecting the strong habitat heterogeneity of the area and the floristic richness associated with montane grassland, wetland, riparian, rocky, and forest habitats. Dolerite Grasslands, Northern Afromontane Forest, Sandstone Grasslands, and Wetland/Riparian Vegetation were identified as particularly important habitats, both in terms of overall species richness and the number of conservation-important taxa they support.

The assessment recorded 14 Species of Conservation Concern, together with rare species, range-extended taxa, potentially new or taxonomically uncertain taxa, decreasing species, and nationally protected tree species. These findings confirm that the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment supports plant taxa of high local, regional, and national significance, and that the remaining natural habitats within the study area retain considerable ecological value. In particular, the occurrence of threatened species and local range extensions highlights the importance of the area not only for conservation, but also for improving understanding of regional plant distributions and habitat associations.

At the same time, the study found that ecological condition and management pressure vary substantially between farms. Some farms remain in relatively intact condition and are currently being managed in a way that appears broadly compatible with biodiversity conservation, while others are under increasing pressure from grazing, alien invasive plants, bracken fern dominance, local wetland disturbance, forest edge invasion, plantation impacts, and habitat transformation. These pressures do not negate the conservation value of the study area, but they do emphasise the importance of active and adaptive management if long-term ecological function is to be maintained.

The long-term conservation of the study area will depend on practical, farm-level management that is responsive to habitat sensitivity and veld condition. Regular monitoring should be used to track ecological change and guide management adjustments over time. Grazing systems should avoid chronic overutilisation and include adequate rest, fire management should maintain habitat heterogeneity and avoid damaging sensitive areas, and invasive plant control should be implemented as a sustained and strategic programme. Particular attention should be given to wetlands, riparian zones, summit areas, rocky habitats, forest patches, and forest margins, as these are often both highly sensitive and disproportionately important for biodiversity.

In conclusion, the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment remains a botanically valuable and ecologically significant landscape that supports a rich and conservation-important flora. The surveyed farms make an important contribution to this value, although their current condition and management needs differ. With appropriate long-term management, continued monitoring, and early intervention where ecological pressures are evident, the biodiversity value of these farms can be retained and strengthened, thereby contributing to future management planning and the broader conservation objectives of the protected environment.

7 References

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